

MareGraph

Towards an Interoperable Marine Knowledge Graph

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Acronyms and Terminology

Terminology/Acronym	Description
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centre
DwC	Darwin Core
DUL	DOLCE + DnS Ultralite (ontology)
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biodiversity Information System
LOD	Linked Open Data
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
ODP	Ontology Design Pattern
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PROV-O	The PROVenance Ontology
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SKOS-XL	Simple Knowledge Organization System – eXtension for Labels
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
TDWG	Taxonomic Databases Working Group / Biodiversity Information Standards
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VLIZ	Flanders Marine Institute
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
XD	eXtreme Design

Executive Summary

This document presents the final versions of the ontologies developed in the MAREGRAPH project. These ontologies are essential for representing data from both the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) and the European Ocean Biodiversity Information System (EurOBIS) according to the Linked Open Data paradigm, thereby significantly enhancing semantic interoperability for identified high-value data.

This document builds upon Deliverable D3.1, which introduced only the preliminary versions of ontologies designed for WoRMS and covering key aspects related to taxonomy and scientific nomenclature of marine species and related information. Here, we offer *a self-contained deliverable* detailing all ontology development within MAREGRAPH. Specifically, it outlines the changes applied to the ontologies previously described in D3.1, and introduces a brand-new ontology called Marine Observations. This new ontology focuses on observations in the biodiversity domain, including the occurrence of organisms, as basis for capturing the informative content of EurOBIS' datasets.

Additionally, this deliverable introduces SHACL shapes defined for each ontology module for validation purposes. SHACL shapes are constraints applied to RDF graphs that can be used to verify whether instances of the ontologies adhere to specific application-dependent constraints. SHACL shapes are, in fact, a well-established method for defining application profiles, which are specifications describing how a standard can be applied to targeted applications.

In essence, the MAREGRAPH network of ontologies currently comprises five domain-specific OWL ontology modules and a top-level OWL ontology. The top-level ontology serves to link various domain entities and to define entities that are domain-independent but crucial for fulfilling modelling requirements. This top-level ontology, extended as described herein, is based on well-known foundational ontologies such as DOLCE.

Finally, a reference example of Linked Open Data for EurOBIS data is provided, mirroring the approach taken in D3.1 (and also part of this document) with data from WoRMS.

As with the previously described ontologies, all versions are publicly available on the project's GitHub repository dedicated to semantic assets: <https://github.com/MareGraph-EU/assets>.

While this deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of the ontologies and related semantic assets, it is important to note that these artifacts are living resources that may evolve over time. Updates may be introduced to accommodate emerging requirements, address new use cases, or incorporate feedback from their application in real-world scenarios. As such, the GitHub repository should be considered the authoritative source for the most up-to-date versions and ongoing development of these semantic assets.

1 Introduction

One of the MAREGRAPH project's primary aims is to enhance the semantic interoperability of a set of high-value datasets identified within the fisheries domain. This is not just about making data available; it is about making it truly usable. To achieve this objective, we are building a robust and interoperable semantic framework. This framework acts as the foundational backbone for an open marine knowledge graph, ensuring that crucial marine datasets are not only discoverable but also readily accessible, genuinely interoperable, understandable, and ultimately reusable by anyone. In essence, we are striving to make them FAIR —Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—in alignment with the well-established principles of open science [1].

Increasing semantic interoperability goes beyond mere data exchange; it demands a deep understanding of data's true meaning and its underlying context. When data is unambiguous and its relationships are clearly defined, it can be analysed far more effectively. This clarity directly translates to more reliable inferences, empowering better-informed decision-making in areas ranging from conservation strategies to sustainable fishing practices. Consider, for example, how consistently defined terms for species occurrences or oceanographic measurements can prevent misinterpretations that might lead to flawed scientific conclusions or inefficient policy interventions.

However, implementing semantic interoperability is far from being a simple task. It requires a significant effort in fostering consensus among diverse stakeholders—from researchers and policymakers to industry representatives—on shared data models and the precise meanings of terms. This collaborative process ensures that everyone involved speaks the same “data language”, minimizing miscommunication and maximizing the utility of information.

This deliverable reports the outcomes of MAREGRAPH's concerted efforts to construct a semantic framework for two important data systems like WoRMS and EurOBIS. This framework is specifically designed to support the effective production of Linked Open Data for the project's identified high-value open datasets. These results derived from discussions and compromises reached through a collaborative dialogue. This dialogue involved not only external project stakeholders (involved through dedicated thematic workshops) but also domain experts from VLIZ (the Flanders Marine Institute) who are the primary custodians of the raw datasets destined for transformation into Linked Open Data. Their knowledge of the data's nuances and complexities has been important in shaping the ontologies to accurately reflect real-world marine phenomena.

Specifically, this document outlines the systematic methodology we followed, building upon the initial groundwork laid out in Deliverable D3.1. It also details the state-of-the-art research we conducted to arrive at the definition of a modular network of ontologies tailored for both the WoRMS and EurOBIS systems. Furthermore, for robust data validation purposes, we have delineated and published so-called SHACL shapes alongside the ontology modules. This deliverable introduces this additional work, highlighting how these SHACL shapes serve as a robust mechanism to ensure data quality and adherence to defined constraints, thereby guaranteeing the reliability of the integrated data.

It is important to acknowledge that one of the most challenging aspects of this project, particularly concerning the development of ontologies fundamental to the semantic interoperability of the identified high-value datasets, has been achieving widespread community consensus. Our aim was to foster greater acceptance and adoption of the ontologies we defined. Despite applying the OSLO process from Work Package 2—a structured methodology designed to build consensus—we found that significant community involvement proved difficult to achieve. This was likely due, in part, to the highly specialized and often vertical nature of the marine biodiversity domain, where experts often operate within very specific niches. This experience underscores the inherent difficulty in bridging diverse perspectives within highly technical fields.

In the same way as D3.1 was influenced by D5.1 – WoRMS/LOD Gap Analysis and was the basis for D5.2 – WoRMS/LOD, this document was influenced by D5.3 – EurOBIS/LOD Gap Analysis and represents the basis for D5.4 – EurOBIS/LOD.

Structure of this document

The remainder of this document is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the detailed methodology we followed throughout the ontology development process, explaining the steps taken from initial conceptualization to final implementation. Section 3 discusses the state of the art, including a thorough review of relevant literature that allowed us to create the brand-new Marine Observation ontology specifically designed for the EurOBIS system, addressing the unique characteristics of observational biodiversity data. Section 4 presents the systematic process of requirement elicitation, outlining how user needs and data characteristics were translated into specific ontological requirements. Section 5 forms the core of this deliverable, showcasing all the ontologies produced; it describes some in terms of changes and refinements made since Deliverable D3.1, while also presenting entirely new ontologies. Section 6 then explores a possible practical application of these ontologies, demonstrating their utility through the use of real data from both the WoRMS and EurOBIS systems. Finally, Section 8 provides a concluding summary of the deliverable’s key achievements and offers insights into future directions.

Relation to D3.1 and changes

As already introduced, this deliverable (D3.2) builds upon and extends the foundation laid by D3.1 and represents an evolution of the concepts, methodologies, and ontologies presented in the earlier work, incorporating new insights, refined approaches, and expanded scope to include new ontology modules based on project progression and stakeholder feedback.

To clarify the relationship between these deliverables and facilitate reader comprehension, in the following we provide a comprehensive overview of the key changes, updates, and additions implemented in D3.2. This itemized presentation highlights both the continuity with D3.1 and the specific enhancements that distinguish this deliverable, ensuring transparency in the development process and enabling the reader to understand the iterative improvements made throughout the project lifecycle. With respect to D3.1, this deliverable includes the changes and additions listed below.

- The Executive Summary, Introduction and Concluding Remarks have been revised to reflect the extended scope of the deliverable.
- Section 2 has been slightly revised to include information about the thematic workshop held on EurOBIS and its impact on the design process.
- Section 3 has been extended to broaden the state of the art analysis and cover biogeographic data as managed in EurOBIS; in particular, Section 3.1 on Darwin Core was extended and four new Sections were added (from 3.9 to 3.12).
- Section 4 has been extended to include requirements, use cases, and competency questions for EurOBIS, as well as a description of the reference data format and contents.
- In Section 5, the diagrams and description of the APHIA ontology modules for WoRMS have been updated to reflect any change since the delivery of D3.1; a new ontology module for marine observations (Section 5.6) and targeting EurOBIS was added.
- Section 6 has been extended to include usage examples for the new ontology module with real-world data from EurOBIS.
- A new Section 7 has been added to cover SHACL shapes that complement the ontology modules for MarineRegions, WoRMS and EurOBIS.

2 Methodology for ontology design and engineering

For the design and implementation of the ontology modules presented in this document, we adhered to a well-defined general process. This approach was initially outlined in Deliverable D2.1 and then reported in D3.1, which collectively established a robust technical methodology for ontology design and engineering. This methodical framework ensured consistency and rigor throughout our development efforts.

A first step in this process involved setting up an internal working group with our key business partner, VLIZ (Flanders Marine Institute). Together, we collaboratively defined a formal Charter, which has since been publicly disseminated on the MAREGRAPH website. This Charter is a declaration of our collective intent to embark on the development of the ontologies (semantic assets) of the project. It lays out the overarching objectives of MAREGRAPH, details the specific high-value datasets identified within the project that are targeted for semantic enhancement, and outlines potential use cases acknowledged and validated by our business partner. Furthermore, it includes a tentative schedule for actively engaging with external stakeholders, fostering a community around the ontology definition process. This community building was important for ensuring the broader relevance and eventual adoption of our semantic assets.

The Charter also provided our plan for a series of workshops designed to engage with external communities relevant to both WoRMS (World Register of Marine Species) and EurOBIS (European Ocean Biogeographic Information System). Our initial outreach began with a first business workshop. During this pivotal session, we presented the MAREGRAPH project, articulated its objectives, and introduced the methodology we intended to follow for the creation of all ontologies and controlled vocabularies.

For the WoRMS system, our engagement strategy included two dedicated thematic workshops. These sessions delved into the complexities of the WoRMS system, explaining its structure and presenting a list of data for potential transformation into Linked Open Data, aligned with specific semantic assets. In contrast, for EurOBIS, we managed to organize only one thematic workshop. This limitation stemmed primarily from difficulties encountered in stakeholder engagement, which proved to be a challenge. Despite these hurdles, this single EurOBIS workshop was a success; it explained the different types of data involved and highlighted the potential complexities and challenges in processing and integrating them.

While overall participation from external stakeholders was somewhat limited, we hosted anyway important representatives from two globally recognized, in the fisheries domain, standards and organizations: the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Taxonomic Databases Working Group (TDWG). Notably, the TDWG representative is also directly involved in the recent on-going work on the Darwin Core Data Package¹, whose goal is to enhance the Darwin Core standard for publishing biodiversity data. Both organizations offered comments and feedback, which we considered and incorporated during the development of our brand-new Marine Observation ontology.

¹ <https://github.com/gbif/dwc-dp/blob/master/README.md#darwin-core-data-package-dwc-dp-publishing-model>

During these thematic workshops, a discussion took place regarding the state of the art of existing ontologies pertinent to the marine domain, the details of which are elaborated in Section 3 of this document. We also presented initial proposals for modelling the data, i.e., so-called draft interim specifications of the process discussed in the deliverable D2.1. The primary objective of these presentations was to actively collect feedback from participants. This feedback was then used in successive steps to continuously refine the ontology design in an agile and iterative manner. This iterative approach allowed us to incorporate expert insights and adapt our designs, ensuring the ontologies remained flexible and responsive to evolving requirements.

Within this collaborative and iterative context, the technical development of the ontologies for both WoRMS and EurOBIS was carried out using a specific methodology known as eXtreme Design with Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs). This approach, further detailed in the subsequent sub-section and referenced in [2] provided a structured yet flexible framework for creating robust and functional semantic assets.

2.1 Ontology Engineering Approach – the XD methodology

The eXtreme Design methodology is collaborative, as it is planned in the OSLO process described in the deliverable D2.1, and shown in a high-level process in Figure 1.

It requires the joint work of teams of *ontology engineers* (ontology design team of Figure 1) and *domain experts*, these latter also coming from the data provider of the project. Moreover, the methodology is incremental and iterative, as the design pairs integrate the modules produced by the other pairs to obtain incremental releases of the ontology.

Figure 1: Ontology design and development process

In Figure 1 we illustrate the most important stages that constitute the XD methodology. The first stage is the collection of requirements and their definition. Requirements can be collected in different forms, from use cases to competency questions definition (see Section 4) up to data extraction from the database (using a more bottom-up approach). Once a set of

requirements has been identified, ontology design is done by going through a state-of-the-art analysis of existing ontologies and so-called Ontology Design Patterns (ODPs).

XD, in fact, relies on the concept of ODPs, which are reusable modelling solutions created to solve recurring ontology modelling problems. We decided to use an ODPs-based approach because there is evidence [3] that the reuse of ODPs can (i) speed up the ontology design process, (ii) ease design choices, (iii) produce more effective results in terms of ontology quality, and (iv) boost (semantic) interoperability, this latter one of the main objectives of the MAREGRAPH project.

In these analyses that trigger the design, top-level (or upper or foundational) ontologies play an important role. These types of ontologies define general concepts (e.g., System, Agent, Topic, Region, etc.) and relationships (e.g., part of, causality, participation) *“that are meant to be basic and universal to ensure generality and expressiveness for a wide range of domains”* [4]. They provide a specific view, with their defined logical axioms, of the world and could be very helpful to: i) understand the semantic essence of what is to be represented; ii) connect different entities in different ontologies; iii) define general elements that are independent of the specific domain.

In the project, we decided to adopt variants of a very famous foundational ontology which is DOLCE [1]. This brought us to model a top-level ontology that also extends some of DOLCE's general concepts with others necessary to meet the gathered requirements (e.g., Identifier, Name, Temporal Entity).

In the design and implementation phase we also apply both a direct and indirect re-use approach of ontologies already publicly available.

With the term direct re-use we mean the practice for which when building a new ontology, existing ontologies as a whole or in parts are *directly* reused by taking classes/concepts and properties from diverse ontologies, usually based on similarities between names of other ontologies entities/properties. If not applied carefully, the selection of the reused properties and classes may cause semantic inconsistencies with the original semantics of the reused terms. This practice, quite common in pure Linked Open Data projects, might bring to create so-called “Frankenstein ontologies” [5].

In contrast, with the term indirect re-use we mean the practice for which when building a new ontology, existing ontologies are *indirectly* reused by defining semantic alignments and mappings to enable interoperability. In this case, the ontology under development has its own well-defined semantics based on the requirements gathered, and the alignment axioms are added, also as possible separate artefacts from the main ontology under design.

For more details on the meaning of direct and indirect re-use of semantic assets in literature, the interested readers can refer to [6].

Table 1 and Table 2 present the advantages and disadvantages of these two approaches, respectively.

Table 1: The pros and cons of the direct re-use of existing ontologies

Direct Reuse Pros	Direct Reuse Cons
It can maximize the reusability and interoperability when reusing standard, authoritative ontologies that are “trust” and “understood” (in a domain)	There could be a semantic misalignment among reused ontologies and with respect to domain requirements. In fact, it happens quite often that reused ontologies may build on different assumptions and lead to inconsistencies when combined with others.
It can help saving time and effort when concepts, relationships and axioms <i>fully</i> satisfy domain requirements	It enables a strong dependency on and coupling with external resources. This also means that if the reused ontology changes or becomes unavailable over time, the entire semantics of the ontology being created on the basis of the direct reuse can be fully compromised
It enhances the acceptance and adoption of the new ontology within the relevant community	Possible modifications to the reused ontology may not be feasible or “appropriate” from a semantic perspective

Table 2: The pros and cons of the indirect re-use of existing ontologies

Indirect Reuse Pros	Indirect Reuse Cons
It allows for a full control over the semantics of the ontology, with <i>stability</i> , <i>robustness</i> and <i>sustainability</i> of fundamental concepts and relationships of the target domain	There could be a potential effort to create and maintain over time alignments and mappings
It enables high flexibility and multiple integration possibilities, with specialization of concepts and relationships (of both domain-specific and general purpose or foundational ontologies) to meet specific requirements	There could be potential challenges when aligning ontologies with different levels of semantic granularity
It preserves <i>interoperability</i> with existing models and community acceptance, without reinventing the wheel	The reuse and alignments may not be immediately apparent or obvious to non-experts

In the design of the ontologies described in this deliverable we decided to use a hybrid approach: when actual standards and Web recommendations from standardisation bodies (i.e., ISO, W3C) include classes and properties corresponding to a strong semantic alignment with what we want to express to meet specific requirements, we use *directly* them. For all the remaining cases, we apply an *indirect reuse* approach, with semantic alignments axioms included in the same ontology artefact being developed in MAREGRAPH.

Once all the elements to be represented have been specified, a modularisation approach is used. This modularisation implies the production of several ontological modules with the top-level ontology being the glue to keep them organised together in a network. This organisation

of knowledge usually also helps in future maintenance procedures with respect to data peculiarities: data may have different management procedures and different update frequencies that may have an impact on the management of their semantic representations.

Finally, it is important to report that when designing ontologies, ontology designers are used to sketch them in some graphical representations. There are different types of graphical notations to be used in order to represent OWL ontologies. Examples include Graffoo [7] and Graphol [8]. Other practices suggest the use of UML class diagrams to represent ontologies, although UML expressivity is not comparable to that offered by languages born with the purpose to create ontologies like OWL.

The graphical representation can be used to document the semantics being implemented, but also as a technical starting point from which to derive the ontology source code, using standards such as RDFSchema and OWL, or the HTML representation of the ontology.

We decided to use Graffoo and in some cases also UML for the graphical representations that are included in this deliverable. At the moment, these are utilised in the communication between ontology designers and internal and external domain experts, and for documentation purposes.

3 Ontologies and data models for biodiversity information

Over the years, various models and ontologies were designed and proposed for the representation and interchange of information about species and, more in general, scientific data on biodiversity. The development of such models is strictly related to the evolution of biodiversity informatics, i.e., the application of informatics techniques to biodiversity information, such as taxonomy, biogeography or ecology. Rich data models are in fact at the heart of biodiversity information systems, such as the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS), which aim at supporting the process of comprehensively cataloguing and organising biological taxa and their scientific names, traits, ecological interactions, distribution, and other biological data, often through the integration of information from diverse sources.

In addition, there exists the European Ocean Biogeographic Information System (EurOBIS), which aims to centralise scattered biogeographic data on marine species collected by European institutions in European waters and to make this data freely available and easily accessible. In particular, its database stores data on taxonomy and occurrence records in space and time. The data model employed by EurOBIS, built upon the principles of events and the Entity-Attribute-Value (EAV) pattern, offers exceptional flexibility in collecting diverse information. This approach means that beyond simply recording organism occurrences, EurOBIS can capture any type of relevant detail. For instance, metadata such as the vessel name—the specific facility used for observation—or the precise sampling method employed can be seamlessly integrated using this pattern. This method of observing and documenting specific values for a potentially open-ended set of attributes associated with entities is a well-established practice in academic literature and is also robustly supported by Semantic Web standards. Its utility is particularly evident in scenarios like the description of attributes and traits of marine resources, that we modelled through a specific ontology module introduced in D3.1, where it's impossible to predefine all future characteristics, thereby providing essential flexibility for accommodating new and evolving data.

A comprehensive data model for representing biodiversity information thus typically encompasses several core elements:

- **Taxa:** this includes the classification of organisms into taxonomic groups with hierarchical relationships, as well as references to authoritative taxonomic sources. This information allows representing the hierarchical structure of biological classification, ranging from broader categories like kingdom and phylum to narrower categories like genus and species.
- **Scientific names:** the formal scientific names used to denote taxa. They typically adhere to the rules of nomenclature established by reference organisations in international codes of nomenclature. The representation and management of scientific names also requires dealing with synonyms, homonyms and other relationships between names and their role as labels for taxa.

- **Identifiers:** to support information exchange and avoid ambiguities, taxa and names typically have unique identifiers within the reference system, facilitating unambiguous reference and integration with other data sources and systems.
- **Traits, attributes and other properties:** this includes observable quantitative or qualitative characteristics of organisms and attributes or properties associated with taxa, such as morphology, behaviour, physiology, life history attributes, and ecological interactions (such as predation, parasitism, etc.).
- **Distribution:** distribution data records where organisms are found geographically, potentially including information on habitats, geographic ranges, species origin and other details.
- **References and sources:** this includes references to authoritative sources, scientific literature, taxonomic databases, and other data providers to support the validity and traceability of taxonomic information and provide context and provenance for biodiversity data.
- **Organisms occurrence and in general assertions or measurement of fact:** this includes tracing occurrence of organisms during specific events (think to an event as a “sampling activity”, a “survey”, a “cruise” etc.) taking place in locations and in time periods. It’s the "who/what, where, and when" of a biological observation. Beyond simply noting an organism’s presence, the context surrounding that observation is equally important This encompasses any quantifiable or descriptive property related to the observed organisms (biotic factors) or their environment (abiotic factors such as water temperature, etc.).

Within the framework of all these elements, as many authors have observed (e.g., [10] [11] [12]), scientific names represent the crucial component in being able to link together information from different sources and disciplines (e.g., literature, geography, genetics, etc.); at the same time, this might also pose problems, e.g., due to the fact that species have received different names over time and the same name has been used for different species. On one side scientific names form the basis for referring to species and they label biodiversity information across the entire spectrum of biodiversity knowledge, but on the other side scientific names can be unstable, imperfect and potentially ambiguous identifiers for taxa (as discussed for example in [13] [14] [15]). As this dichotomy between scientific names and taxa plays an important role, it represents one of the core aspects considered in the main data models and ontologies presented and summarised hereafter.

The goal of this section is thus to introduce and summarise the primary aspects of the main data models used to represent and exchange biodiversity-related data. While our main focus is on ontological models, we also consider existing relevant models that do not necessarily have an ontological representation (e.g., Darwin Core).

3.1 Darwin Core (DwC)

Darwin Core² is the *de facto standard* for representing and sharing biodiversity information [17]. Conceived as an extension of Dublin Core, it is part of the biodiversity information standards maintained by the Taxonomic Databases Working Group (TDWG). Darwin Core (DwC) defines and makes available a glossary of terms (basically classes and properties), definitions and guidelines for representing taxa, their occurrence in nature (as documented by observations, specimens, samples) and related information. DwC is widely used in biodiversity informatics and serves as a foundation for data sharing among various platforms, including biodiversity databases, research projects, and other initiatives. An overview of the main categories or classes of information that can be represented using Darwin Core is provided in Figure 2. The available classes or categories are subject to revisions and extensions, and additional classes or categories were defined since the initial release; some of them are directly "borrowed" from Dublin Core. For the full set of current Darwin Core terms with their descriptions, please refer to <https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/>.

Record-level Terms	Dublin Core terms, institutions, collections, nature of data record	Simple Darwin Core (flat)
Occurrence	evidence of species in nature, observers, behavior, associated media, references.	
Event	sampling protocols and methods, date, time, field notes	
Location	geography, locality descriptions, spatial data	
Identification	linkage between Taxon and Occurrence	
Taxon	scientific names, vernacular names, names usages, taxon concepts, and the relationships between them	
GeologicalContext	geologic time, chrono-stratigraphy, biostratigraphy, lithostratigraphy	
ResourceRelationship	explicit relationships between identified resources (e.g., one organism to another, taxon to location, etc.)	Generic Darwin Core (relational)
MeasurementOrFact	measurements, facts, characteristics, assertions, references	

Figure 2: Overview of Darwin Core categories for representing biodiversity data. Source [16].

Fundamental to our analysis and discussion are a set of classes that are to be considered for both WoRMS and EurOBIS system. The first class is DwC's Taxon, whose definition and properties are shown in Figure 3.

² <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

Figure 3: Definition and properties for Dwc Taxon class

In DwC, the Taxon class plays a crucial role in describing taxonomic information related to organisms, as it allows representing taxonomic entities such as species, genera, families, and other taxonomic ranks within biodiversity datasets. The Taxon class includes properties for representing both taxonomic and nomenclatural information, such as scientific names, taxon ranks, taxonomic status and hierarchical relationships between taxa (indicating parent-child relationships within taxonomic classifications), as well as vernacular names and references to sources. Darwin Core thus conflates taxonomy and nomenclature information within a single class, reflecting the pragmatic approach taken to address the practical needs of biodiversity data sharing and integration. While such an approach may offer practical benefits for biodiversity data management and exchange, it may not fully capture the complexities and nuances of the domain in case an explicit distinction has to be made between taxa and the names used to label or refer to them.

In the context of EurOBIS data, the classes related to event, occurrence of organisms and additional measurements or facts are the reference components to be taken into account in Darwin Core, since the EurOBIS data is based on the OBIS global database which builds upon those Darwin Core classes. The following FiguresFigure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6 show their definitions and the set of properties that are associated with them.

Figure 4: Definition and properties for Dwc Event class

Figure 5: Definition and properties for Dwc Occurrence class

Figure 6: Definition and properties for Dwc MeasurementOrFact class

One limitation of the conceptual model proposed by Darwin Core for its core classes, such as *Event*, lies in its adherence to a “flat modelling approach”. This design choice, while offering simplicity in some contexts, can lead to semantic ambiguities and a less granular representation of data than might be ideal for advanced analytical needs.

For instance, within the *Event* class, certain properties are directly associated with a sample, presumably one produced during a specific sampling event. However, from a strict semantic perspective, these properties—such as sample size value and unit—are intrinsically linked to the sample object itself rather than to the event that generated it. While the event is the context of sample creation, the physical characteristics of the sample are properties of that distinct entity. This practice may obscure the precise relationships between the sampling activity, the resulting sample, and the observations made from that sample.

A similar observation applies to how temporal properties are handled. In Darwin Core, time-related attributes (like year, month) are directly attached to the *Event* class. However, in most robust foundational ontologies and indeed in common logical modelling practices, an event is understood to *have* a temporal dimension, which is itself a distinct entity characterized by properties like date, year, month, and specific time values. By directly embedding these temporal details within the *Event* class, Darwin Core's model diverges from a more semantically precise representation where a temporal entity (e.g., a Time Interval or

Temporal Entity) is explicitly associated with an event, and it is that temporal entity which possesses the granular time-based properties. This "flattening" of temporal information can make it more challenging to perform temporal queries or reason about the chronology and duration of events.

Furthermore, another drawback observed in the practical application of Darwin Core is the widespread tendency to use simple strings for data values, even when the usage notes explicitly recommend the adoption of controlled vocabularies. While Darwin Core strongly encourages the use of standardized terms (e.g., for `basisOfRecord`, `occurrenceStatus`), this recommendation is often not strictly enforced or widely adopted in practice. This pervasive use of unstructured or free-text strings leads to less structured data than could be achieved, hindering true semantic interoperability. Without the consistent application of controlled vocabularies, data analysis becomes more challenging due to variations in terminology, spelling errors, and synonyms. This lack of standardization limits the ability to effectively aggregate, compare, and query data across different datasets, ultimately reducing the overall discoverability, accessibility, and reusability of valuable biodiversity information.

In any case, a detailed usage guide is also provided on how to use Darwin Core for RDF data³. Nevertheless, the RDF guide basically highlights that the usage of classes and properties generally follows a loosely specified semantics. So while in principle *"any Darwin Core class IRI MAY be used as a value for rdf:type"*, DwC does not declare domains for its property terms and the application of properties to instances of classes presented in reference guide has to be considered as a suggestion. More in details, when it comes to the description of a taxonomic entity, the RDF guide explicitly states that for the properties listed in Figure 3 *"it is NOT RECOMMENDED to use these as properties of dwc:Taxon instances"*. The guide further states that *"the object properties necessary to relate dwc:Taxon instances to name entities, references, parent taxa, and child taxa do not exist and the exact relationship between taxonomic entities such as taxon concepts, protonyms, taxon name usages, etc. has not been established using RDF. So the creation of functional dwc:Taxon instances described using RDF is not possible at the present time"*. On one side the loosely defined semantics of the properties allows reusing them in different settings, but on the other side the guidelines basically suggest that DwC is not to be considered as a ready-to-use straightforward ontology for representing taxonomic entities in RDF. To partially overcome this limitation, the guide suggests considering the TDWG Taxon Concept Transfer Schema (TCS) standard for representing taxonomic entities; however, TCS is defined as an XML schema only, without explicit support for RDF (see section below for additional details on TCS).

Regardless of these aspects, DwC plays a central role in the representation of biodiversity-related data for both WoRMS and EuroBIS and this was taken into account in the design and implementation of all our proposed ontology modules.

³ Darwin Core RDF guide - <https://dwc.tdwg.org/rdf/>

3.2 Taxon Concept Schema (TCS) and TCS 2

Taxon Concept Schema (TCS) is a TDWG standard⁴ defined for representing and exchanging taxonomic data. It was designed for representing taxon concepts as defined in various sources like published classifications, revisions, and databases. It is technically defined as an XML Schema which specifies the structure for XML documents used to transfer these concepts. The schema allows representing taxa by either explicitly detailing all defining components, or by using Globally Unique Identifiers (GUIDs) that refer to existing defined concepts, if and when available. TCS makes an explicit distinction between taxon names and taxon concepts, owing to the observations that one name may be used to denote several concepts, and that names are governed by nomenclature rules and codes that are separate from those for concepts. The overall approach of TCS is rooted in the principle of considering a taxon concept as a name plus a description of a taxon, referring thus to the source (e.g., a published paper) where, or according to, the location of the circumscription is defined. TCS is also designed to allow representing potentially competing and conflicting classifications, and thus multiple taxonomic opinions. This goes beyond the requirements for representing the data coming from WoRMS, where a single integrated taxonomic classification and perspective is provided.

Despite the advanced problems that TCS aimed at addressing and the valuable attempt to represent taxonomic concepts in a structured and standardised manner, the uptake and adoption of TCS were and are limited, also due to its complexity, and the standard is basically considered outdated.

Figure 7: Overview of TCS2 data model (May 2025). Source: <https://github.com/tdwg/tcs2>

⁴ <http://www.tdwg.org/standards/117>

To overcome these limitations, the Taxonomic Concept Schema (TCS2) Task Group⁵ is working to create a new version of TCS⁶ as a full-fledged semantic vocabulary that defines and makes available classes and properties, together with the definition or identification of controlled vocabularies for specific properties (such as taxonomic ranks, nomenclatural status of names, etc.). As in the case of TCS, TCS2 is rooted in the distinction between taxon concepts and taxon names, as well as on the need and possibility of defining relationships between concepts and between names (in addition to relating names and concepts). Again as in TCS, a taxon concept can be identified through the combination of a label, referred to as the taxon name (not necessarily representing canonical scientific names), along with its respective source information (the *accordingTo* dimension). Although not yet finalised by the working group (as of February 2024), the diagram in Figure 7 provides a good overview of the core entities and how they are related, although potentially subject to changes as the work of the group progresses.

There is clearly a strong overlap in the requirements addressed by TCS2 and those that are being considered in the context of MAREGRAPH. TCS2 is expected to provide "the best of" taxonomic data representation, also capitalising on previous experiences and lessons learned from the development and implementation of TCS. The ongoing work of the task group is a valuable source of inspiration for the design of the ontology modules in MAREGRAPH, and we expect that it will be possible to define clear semantic alignments between our modules and the upcoming TCS2 ontology (under the assumption that an OWL ontology will be produced).

3.3 The OpenBioDiv Ontology

The OpenBioDiv Ontology (OpenBiodiv-O) [18] aims at providing classes, properties, and axioms to support knowledge representation in the domains of scholarly biodiversity publishing and biological taxonomy. As defined by its authors "*it is an ontology of the scientific process of biological taxonomy and not of any particular state of knowledge*", thus aiming at supporting the expression of multiple scientific opinions concerning taxa, their naming and possible classifications and relationships. The OpenBioDiv Ontology is intended as the reference ontology for the Open Biodiversity Knowledge Management System⁷.

OpenBiodiv-O⁸ is designed to allow capturing up to a specific mention of a scientific name in a scientific article, also relying on well-established ontologies and patterns for scholarly data and bibliographic information, specifically the Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies (SPAR Ontologies) [19]. When it comes to represent the taxonomic and nomenclatural perspectives, OpenBiodiv-O makes an explicit distinction between taxonomic concepts and the names used to denote them. Figure 8 provides an overview of the approach taken to represent taxonomic concepts. The figure also shows the equivalence relationship

⁵ <https://www.tdwg.org/community/tnc/tcs2/>

⁶ <https://github.com/tdwg/tcs2>

⁷ OpenBiodiv, <http://openbiodiv.net/>

⁸ <https://github.com/vsenderov/openbiodiv-o>

(`owl:equivalentClass`) defined between the Taxonomic Concept class and the Taxon class available in Darwin Core.

Figure 8: Taxonomic concept in OpenBiodiv-O [18]

Taxonomic concepts are then related to taxonomic names, which are then further specialised to capture the different kinds of names that can be used in relation to taxa, ranging from vernacular names to scientific names, to fully specified taxonomic concept labels that combine a scientific name with a source where the name is used and the implied taxonomic concept is defined. The approach taken to represent scientific names is depicted in Figure 9: Taxonomic names in OpenBiodiv-O [18].

Figure 9: Taxonomic names in OpenBiodiv-O [18]

Additional specific properties, as discussed for in the previous section, are defined to allow linking taxonomic concepts and express taxonomic concept relationships that go beyond hierarchical, taxonomic parent-child relationships.

OpenBiodiv-O, as also discussed by other authors [13], ties the distinction between taxa and names to semiotics theory, and in particular to the well-known semiotic triangle, which explores the relationship between signs, objects, and interpretations. Under this view, a scientific name is a sign, symbol or label that evokes or denotes a taxonomic concept, and is

used to refer to or label an observed specimen as a physical example of an organism belonging to the conceptualised taxon.

While designed to create a link between biodiversity publishing and biological taxonomy, OpenBiodiv-O includes semantically sound modelling solutions that were taken into account for the design of the ontology modules in MAREGRAPH. In addition, the ontology includes domain-specific relevant semantic alignments to other domain ontologies, such as the NOMEN ontology (a nomenclatural ontology for biological names⁹) and the ENVO Environment Ontology¹⁰, which were taken into account as well.

3.4 Bioschemas Taxon and TaxonName profiles

Bioschemas¹¹ is an initiative that extends the existing vocabulary of Schema.org to better describe resources related to life sciences. This has the goal of enabling a richer and more uniform representation of biological data across various platforms and applications, to facilitate data sharing, integration, and discovery within the life sciences community.

Bioschemas defines various “profiles”, defined as “*a community agreed layer over the Schema.org vocabulary*”, which are essentially classes (types) and sets of properties designed to describe specific entities in the life sciences domain. These profiles act as templates, providing a common framework for annotating different types of biological information.

In this context, the working group focusing on biodiversity has defined two reference profiles with classes, properties and constraint for representing taxa (Taxon profile¹², based on the Taxon type) and taxon names (TaxonName profile¹³, based on the TaxonName type). Bioschemas profiles thus follow the knowledge representation approach already discussed for TCS and OpenBiodiv-O, where taxa and their names are treated as distinct entities. More in detail:

- a Taxon, defined as set of organisms asserted to represent a natural cohesive biological unit, can have a taxonomic rank and can be related to other taxa with parent-child relationships to induce a taxonomic classification; a Taxon can be related to taxon names with properties for denoting the currently valid/accepted name and synonyms;
- a TaxonName, defined as a name of a biological taxon, may it be valid (zoology) / accepted (botany) or not, can have a rank as well, and then relies on the existing schema.org name and author properties to allow defining the scientific name and the author.

Although not conceived as a full-fledged ontology for representing biodiversity-related information on species, Bioschemas profiles capture the heart of WoRMS data, also

⁹ <https://github.com/SpeciesFileGroup/nomen>

¹⁰ <https://sites.google.com/site/environmentontology/>

¹¹ <https://bioschemas.org/>

¹² <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/Taxon>

¹³ <https://bioschemas.org/profiles/TaxonName>

considering that the profiles explicitly target web portals and data registries such as GBIF and Catalogue of Life. It is also worth mentioning that, as of the release of version 13 of schema.org, the Taxon type is considered as Schema.org type with reference URI <https://schema.org/Taxon>. Considering the widespread adoption of schema.org, at least as an “annotation” vocabulary for data mark-up on web pages, it is important to recognise its role and define at least semantic alignments that allow considering the data from the “schema.org perspective”.

3.5 TAXREF-LD

TAXREF-LD [20] is a Linked Data knowledge graph representing TAXREF, the French national taxonomic register for fauna, flora, and fungi.

To provide a structured and consistent representation of taxonomic information, TAXREF-LD¹⁴ directly relies on OWL and SKOS so that OWL classes are used to represent taxa and SKOS concepts to represent scientific names. The approach for representing taxonomic and nomenclatural information is quite similar to the one that characterises Bioschemas (Franck Michel, leading author of TAXREF-LD, also co-leads the Bioschemas biodiversity group), with a distinction between taxa and names, which are related to each other.

Figure 10: Taxa and names in TAXREF-LD [20]

¹⁴ <https://github.com/frmichel/taxref-ld>

Figure 10 exemplifies the knowledge representation approach adopted for separating nomenclatural and from taxonomic information. Specifically:

- taxa are represented as OWL classes, and the taxonomic hierarchy is defined relying on `rdfs:subClassOf` relationships; a taxon can have a rank and is related to a reference name (the valid/accepted name) and to synonym names (if any);
- scientific names are represented as SKOS concepts, with properties to define the name and the authority.

TAXREF-LD goes beyond basic taxonomic data (scientific names, ranks, parent taxa) and covers additional aspects including vernacular names, habitat and biogeographical information, species interactions, legal and conservation statuses, cross-references to other biodiversity resources (including WoRMS) and links to media resources like photos.

The solutions adopted in TAXREF-LD are highly relevant for producing a reference ontology and Linked Open Data version of WoRMS, both from knowledge representation perspective (in particular for the usage of standardised ontologies and vocabularies for representing taxonomic and nomenclatural information) and in terms of domain coverage beyond taxonomy and nomenclature (with structured and semantically rich representations for species attributes and other information).

3.6 The Marine Top Level Ontology

The Marine Top Level Ontology¹⁵ (MarineTLO), defined by the Information System Laboratory (ISL) of the Institute of Computer Science (ICS) in the Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), is a top-level OWL ontology designed to facilitate the representation and integration of information from the marine domain.

MarineTLO provides a semantic framework for representing knowledge about marine species. It establishes a structured ontology for describing various aspects of marine life, including taxonomy, nomenclature, distribution, ecology and biological parameters.

Although the ontology is no longer actively maintained, its relevance for the marine domain is still high, also considering concrete application scenarios that were addressed relying on the ontology, such as the setup of a MarineTLO-based Warehouse integrating data from sources such as FishBase and WoRMS. As a top-level ontology, it provides reference high level concepts and properties that can be reused or extended as needed.

The relevance to our work also comes from the approach and methodology used, as the ontology was developed adopting an iterative and incremental methodology. Fully in line with our methodology, the design was driven by the identification of a set of competency questions formulated with the help of domain experts to first capture domain requirements and then evaluate the ontology.

¹⁵ <https://projects.ics.forth.gr/isl/MarineTLO/>

3.7 The Catalogue Of Life Data Package specification

All existing global species databases and biodiversity information systems that act as repositories of information about various species, their distributions, habitats, ecological roles, etc. rely on data models that allow representing taxonomic classifications and nomenclature, species distributions, ecological traits, data sources and other attributes. In addition to WoRMS, well known examples include the Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS), FishBase and SeaLifeBase, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Catalogue of Life.

As a representative example, we consider here the Catalogue of Life¹⁶ (CoL), a global species checklist and index of known species of animals, plants, fungi, and microorganisms, built by aggregating more than 100 species checklists collected from various data providers and sources. WoRMS itself is among the core data providers for CoL.

To enable the collection and integration of data, CoL relies on the so-called Catalogue of Life Data Package¹⁷ (CoLDP), a rich object-oriented domain model that defines the reference exchange format for data. The reference model allows representing taxa and scientific names as separate entities, which are then related to each other to build taxonomic classifications and define accepted names and synonyms. The model also covers relationships between taxa and between names, as well as data sources and references, vernacular names, species distribution, media objects and other attributes. While the reference data model considers taxa and scientific names as different entities, CoLDP includes a variant of the model where taxa and names, as well as taxonomic and nomenclatural attributes and properties, are merged in a single *NameUsage* entity (which resembles the *Taxon* class in DwC). This allows collecting data also from data providers that do not necessarily make a distinction between taxa and names in their data models and datasets. The diagrams in the CoLDP GitHub repository help understanding the overall structure of the data model. These models are also used to “reshape” data from WoRMS and provide it to CoL.

CoLDP, although not formalised as an ontology, is quite relevant for the modelling effort done in MAREGRAPH, as it covers at least a part of the domain-specific entities and properties that characterise the data managed in WoRMS. The relevance of CoLDP, and the roots of modelling and design choices, also emerge from a recent comparison with the Taxon Concept Schema (TCS) standard (introduced before in Section 3.2), where the compatibility between the two models is discussed [21].

3.8 INSPIRE Data Specification on Species Distribution

In the European context, it is important to mention and consider the INSPIRE Data Specification on Species Distribution¹⁸. This INSPIRE data specification, which focuses on the “Species Distribution” category of spatial data defined in the INSPIRE Directive, is a framework

¹⁶ <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/CatalogueOfLife/coldp>

¹⁸ https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/publications/inspire-data-specification-species-distribution-technical-guidelines_en

designed to facilitate the sharing and integration of data related to the distribution of species across geographical regions, in line with the overall aim of the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE) to enable the interoperability of spatial data infrastructures within the European Union. The INSPIRE data specifications are also relevant in the context of the common European data spaces.

The specification defines data models and guidelines for the collection, management, and dissemination of data pertaining to species distribution, including information on species occurrences and habitats. The data specification covers the *“Geographical distribution of occurrence of animal and plant species aggregated by grid, region, administrative unit or other analytical unit.”*, and it thus have a strong relevance for species occurrence data that is considered in MAREGRAPH in relation to the EurOBIS information system and data. The INSPIRE data specification covers entities that have relevance when representing and describing species. In the data model, distribution information is linked to species names denoting the species for which the information is collected and provided. Species names refer to species through a unique identifier, which should be taken from one of three recognised European Classification systems and classification schemes for species, namely EU-Nomen¹⁹ (the preferred reference list), EUNIS and Natura2000. Additional attributes allow defining and referencing the scientific name (with authority info) used in a national nomenclature database of the data-providing country, as well as the reference scheme where the local taxonomic concept is defined. The local taxonomic concept can then be related to the concept defined by the reference species classification scheme (i.e., EU-Nomen, EUNIS or Natura2000).

It is worth highlighting that the infrastructure that supports the EU-Nomen portal and the corresponding Pan-European Species directory Infrastructure (PESI) – considered as the preferred reference list for species in the INSPIRE specification, as mentioned before – is basically the Aphia database that powers WoRMS, in the form of the European Register of Marine Species (ERMS). There is thus a full compatibility between the possibility to shape species occurrence data according to the INSPIRE data specification and the need to reference marine species as represented in WoRMS.

3.9 INSPIRE Data Specification on Observation & Measurement

An additional INSPIRE specification to be taken into account, especially for the EurOBIS system, is the so-called “Observation & Measurement” specification. It provides a standardized conceptual model and encoding rules for representing observations, measurements, and related sampling activities across diverse environmental domains.

At its heart, the INSPIRE O&M Specification is built upon the international standard ISO 19156:2011, Geographic information — Observations and Measurements. This ISO standard provides a comprehensive and domain-neutral conceptual schema for how observations and measurements should be described in a spatially enabled data environment. The INSPIRE

¹⁹ <http://www.eu-nomen.eu/portal/>

O&M Specification then tailors and profiles this general ISO standard to meet the specific requirements and mandates of the INSPIRE Directive within a European context.

The primary purpose of the INSPIRE O&M Specification is to enhance the interoperability of environmental observation data that is collected, managed, and shared by various public authorities across European Union Member States. In essence, it provides a common "language" and structure for reporting data obtained from sensors, monitoring stations, surveys, and other observational processes. This standardization is crucial for enabling the seamless combination and analysis of environmental information from different sources, eliminating the need for extensive manual harmonization efforts.

Figure 11: INSPIRE Observation & Measurement conceptual model

Figure 11 shows an example of a ship measuring the salinity (abiotic factor) at varying depths along a water column, the *featureOfInterest* being a vertical water column at one given ship location.

The INSPIRE O&M Specification defines a consistent way to represent the core components of an observation, including the observed property (what is being measured, e.g., air temperature, water salinity), the feature of interest (the real-world object or phenomenon being observed, e.g., a specific river segment, an air quality zone), the procedure (how the observation was made, including sensor type or methodology), the result (the actual measured value), and the result time (when the observation was made).

Unlike simpler data models, O&M emphasizes the importance of context. It ensures that not just the measurement itself is provided, but also metadata about how it was obtained. This includes details about the sensing device, the sampling strategy, and the environmental conditions, which are all crucial for assessing the quality, provenance, and fitness-for-purpose of the data. For example, knowing if a water temperature reading came from a calibrated

sensor or a simple handheld thermometer, and the depth at which it was taken, significantly impacts its usability.

The INSPIRE O&M Specification often works in conjunction with other Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards, particularly those within the Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) suite, such as the Sensor Observation Service (SOS). This allows for the dynamic access and sharing of real-time or near real-time sensor data within the INSPIRE infrastructure.

3.10 The BiGe-Onto Ontology

Addressing the complexities and semantic limitations often found in traditional biodiversity data management, particularly those identified in flat models like Darwin Core, researchers have developed more sophisticated ontological solutions. One such notable effort is the BiGe-Onto ontology.

BiGe-Onto (Biodiversity and Biogeography Ontology) was introduced as the core ontology within an ontology-based system designed to manage and integrate biodiversity and biogeography data, drawing specifically from internationally recognized public repositories such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS). The primary motivation behind its development, as detailed in [22] stems from the observation that while significant progress has been made in digitizing global biodiversity data, managing and leveraging information from diverse providers and research domains remains a substantial challenge. Existing standards, including Darwin Core, were deemed insufficient for describing biodiversity data in a truly semantically meaningful and computationally useful way, often leading to heterogeneity and limited interoperability.

The BiGe-Onto system aims to bridge this gap by providing a more rigorous and semantically rich conceptualization of biodiversity and biogeography data. A central feature of BiGe-Onto is its capacity to manage data from both biodiversity (focusing on species and their characteristics) and biogeography (focusing on the spatial distribution of species). By creating a unified conceptual model, it enables researchers to ask complex questions that span these traditionally separate domains, such as "How are specific species distributed across certain environmental regions?" or "Which species co-exist in a particular marine area?".

The BiGe-Onto initiative is presented as a complete ontology-based system. This typically includes: a formal conceptual model, often specified in methodologies like OntoUML; an operational version of the ontology, encoded in a machine-readable language like OWL 2; an integrated dataset transformed into a Linked Open Data format; and a SPARQL endpoint for querying and exploiting the integrated data.

While aiming for semantic richness BiGe-ONTO leverages and extends concepts from existing well-established vocabularies and ontologies where appropriate. For instance, its description indicates it uses terms from Darwin Core vocabulary for Occurrence and Organism, and definitions from the ENVO (Environmental Ontology) for environmental concepts. This promotes interoperability with current practices while refining the semantic foundations.

Figure 12 shows the combined usage of different models in BiGe-Onto (Darwin core, Envo, GeoSPARQL, TIME etc.), in order to better structure the relationships between all these elements that characterise biodiversity and biogeography data.

Figure 12: BiGe-Onto Ontology [22]

By providing a formally structured knowledge base, BiGe-Onto supports advanced semantic querying and inference capabilities. This means users can pose more complex questions than simple keyword searches, allowing for the discovery of hidden connections and patterns across disparate datasets that would otherwise be difficult to uncover. Examples include inferring predator-prey relationships or identifying co-occurring species within specific marine regions.

3.11 The Semantic Sensor Network Ontology

The Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN) is a W3C Recommendation published by the World Wide Web Consortium and based on the RDF standard of the Semantic Web. It provides a conceptual model for describing sensors and their observations, the procedures involved in making those observations, the features of interest being observed (i.e., the real-world entities whose properties are being measured), the properties that are observed, and even samples used in the process. It also extends to cover actuators and actuation, which are devices that perform actions based on sensor data.

A key design principle of the SSN Ontology is its modular architecture, which includes a lightweight but self-contained core ontology called SOSA (Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator). SOSA defines the essential classes and properties for describing sensors, observations, samples, and actuators, providing a minimal yet powerful set of terms for basic

interoperability. SSN then builds upon SOSA, adding further axiomatization and terms to support more complex use cases and detailed descriptions of sensor capabilities, systems, and deployment. This modularity allows users to adopt just enough semantics for their specific application needs, ranging from simple data annotations to complex reasoning tasks.

The SSN Ontology addresses several limitations often found in simpler data models:

- *Contextualization of Observations*: Unlike models that might just capture a value, SSN ensures that an observation is always linked to what was observed (the observed property), what feature of interest it pertains to, and how it was observed (the procedure, including the sensor or system used). This rich context is crucial for understanding the provenance, quality, and reliability of the data.
- *Detailed Sensor Capabilities*: SSN allows for the description of a sensor's capabilities, such as its measurement range, accuracy, precision, and operating conditions. This enables sophisticated discovery mechanisms, allowing users to find sensors that can measure a specific property within a certain range or with a required level of accuracy.
- *System and Deployment Information*: The ontology can represent how sensors are integrated into larger systems (e.g., a weather station composed of multiple individual sensors) and how these systems are deployed in the environment. This provides information about the context of data collection.

The development of SSN involved a collaborative effort between the W3C and the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), aiming to bridge the gap between Semantic Web technologies and the established OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) standards, also taken into account by the INSPIRE Observation & Measurement Specification introduced in Section 3.9. This collaboration has resulted in an ontology that is both semantically rich and aligned with existing geospatial data practices.

Figure 13: Observation modelling in the W3C SSN ontology

Figure 13 shows a piece of the modelling offered by SSN related to Observations done by Sensors, in turn hosted by Platforms, of specific Properties of Feature of Interests and that produce Results in certain time periods and using specific Procedures.

3.12 Additional data models related to observations

The countries involved in the MAREGRAPH project, i.e., Italy and Belgium, has worked on semantic assets available in national catalogues that can be considered relevant for modelling certain types of data of EurOBIS.

In particular, Italy developed both a general Internet of Things ontology presented in [23] whose design pattern is based on the modelling pattern offered by the SSN ontology described in Section 3.11, and a set of ontology modules regarding the monitoring of abiotic factors related to weather and water. These modules have been created in the context of a CEF-funded European project named WHOW (Water Health Open knowLedge)²⁰²¹ and are extensively described in [24] All these semantic assets are provided using Semantic Web standards and some of them are used when producing Linked Open Data of some Italian public administrations, both central and local.

Also Belgium, in the Flanders region, provides a vocabulary for Air and Water measurements. The vocabulary consists of a core²² and two modules for air quality²³ and water quality²⁴. Overall, the models are based on the SSN ontology earlier discussed, and have been developed in the context of another CEF-funded project named ODALA. These models are used in the work that Flanders region is carrying out of construction of smart data spaces.

²⁰ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/water-monitoring>

²¹ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/weather-monitoring>

²² <https://purl.eu/ns/air-and-water/core/>

²³ <https://purl.eu/ns/air-and-water/air/>

²⁴ <https://purl.eu/ns/air-and-water/water/>

4 Requirements collection

In order to design the ontologies modules for both WoRMS and EurOBIS, we collected requirements with stakeholders and looking at the data of the two systems.

The requirements have been gathered during different phases of the methodology:

- internal interactions with VLIZ domain experts. In this case, specific requests of data representation and data exports were provided to the modellers to better understand the data to be represented with the ontologies;
- public interactions with people from the community who participated in the various workshops; in particular, the first business workshop in which the topics addressed by MAREGRAPH were presented, the thematic workshops on WoRMS and EurOBIS, in which the ontologies for both systems in their initial versions were discussed and presented.

We identify three types of different requirements that guided the ontology modules design and development:

1. *user cases*;
2. *competency questions*;
3. *data details* coming directly from the data models and databases.

In the following subsection we present the different types of requirements we considered to produce the network of ontologies presented in Section 5.

4.1 Use cases for WoRMS

During the first business workshop we asked stakeholders to identify use cases of interest to them for all possible datasets of the MAREGRAPH project. With the term use case we mean a specific situation of data exchange for which ontologies can be used.

We classified the use cases listed and discussed during the workshops; in Table 3 we report those related to the data contained in WoRMS.

In Table 3 words are in bold to highlight important entities of the domain to be modelled. Some words are not only pertinent for the sole WoRMS (e.g., species distribution) but in general for the project (e.g., species occurrences).

Table 3: Use case definition for WoRMS data during workshops with external stakeholders

Use Case ID	Use Case description
US-W1	I would like to have use cases which can help users to integrate data about distribution, occurrences and functional traits of marine species
US-W2	To be able to follow translation path-ways between scientific taxonomic references and common or commercial language names for marine species
US-W3	The ability to query the graph using semantics that I'm used to (e.g., generic semantic conventions like schema.org or research-focused standards like DCAT)
US-W4	To enable tracking how the taxonomic reference changed over time and how that affects the interpretation of data published at those specific times
US-W5	To enable publishing datapoints and datasets linked to up the reference marine-regions and marine-species (and sub elements of their setup: place types, geographic relations, traits, ...)
US-W6	I want to be able to obtain the most up-to-date taxonomic information for marine species

Specific mention should be made for USW4, which requires the ability to track changes in taxonomic information for marine species over time. At present, there is no specific ontology design pattern related to time-indexed situations that has been implemented in the ontology network due to the lack of this type of data in the WoRMS database. However, evolutions in scientific names and taxonomic classification can be produced in the linked open data according to the so-called taxon name ontology module we have developed (see Section 5.2).

Understanding the relationship between use cases and their potential stakeholders is crucial for successful ontology design in biodiversity informatics. Each use case represents specific needs and workflows that different user communities may have when working with marine biodiversity data. By identifying the stakeholders most likely to benefit from or contribute to each use case, we can better prioritize development efforts, ensure comprehensive requirements gathering, and design ontologies that serve real-world applications. The following analysis maps each use case to its relevant stakeholder communities.

Table 4: Relation between use cases and stakeholders (WoRMS)

Use Case	Stakeholders
US-W1 – Integrating distribution, occurrences, and functional traits of marine species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine ecologists • Conservation biologists • Fisheries scientists • Marine protected area managers • Climate change researchers • Biogeographers • Species distribution modelers

Use Case	Stakeholders
US-W2 – Translation pathways between scientific taxonomic references and common/commercial names	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fisheries managers • Commercial fishers and seafood industry • Fish market operators • Food safety regulators • Consumer protection agencies • Marine taxonomists • Seafood traceability professionals
US-W3 – Query using familiar semantic web conventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semantic Web experts • Knowledge/data engineers • Software/Web developers • Linked data specialists
US-W4 – Tracking taxonomic reference changes over time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxonomists • Systematic biologists • Museum curators • Nomenclature specialists • Historical ecology researchers
US-W5 – Publishing datapoints linked to reference marine regions and species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine data publishers • Research institutions • RFMOs and Government agencies (e.g., ICES, GFCM, NOAA, fisheries departments) • International organizations (e.g., OBIS, GBIF) • Oceanographic institutes (e.g., BODC)
US-W6 – Obtaining up-to-date taxonomic information for marine species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine biologists and taxonomists • Species identification specialists • Field researchers • Taxonomic database maintainers • Reference collection managers

4.2 Use cases for EurOBIS

Throughout the project's lifespan, commencing with the initial business workshop, a set of use cases emerged. These use cases were not merely hypothetical; rather, they were directly suggested by our community stakeholders based on their working experience with data related to the MAREGRAPH project and, in this section, particularly pertinent for the data stored within the EurOBIS system.

Table 5, presented below, details these use cases. For clarity, important keywords within each use case are highlighted in bold, signifying entities or classes identified for ontological modelling.

Table 5: Use cases related to EurOBIS data

Use Case ID	Use Case description
US-E1	Combine biotic and abiotic data information
US-E2	I would like to be able to combine, aggregate, consolidate marine-biodiversity data points regardless of the taxonomic reference system they used
US-E3	I would like to have use cases which can help users to integrate data about distribution, occurrences and functional traits of marine species
US-E4	I would like to query the correlation between marine species observations and fishing boats locations from AIS data, for example
US-E5	MSFD - Descriptor 1: Good Environmental Status in relation to biological diversity

As for the use cases related to WoRMS, the following analysis maps each use case for EurOBIS to its relevant stakeholder communities.

Table 6: Relation between use cases and stakeholders (EurOBIS)

Use Case	Stakeholders
US-E1 – Combine biotic and abiotic data information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine ecosystem researchers • Oceanographers • Environmental data scientists • Policy makers • Water quality researchers
US-E2 – Combine, aggregate, consolidate marine-biodiversity data points regardless of taxonomic reference system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data integration specialists • Biodiversity informatics experts • Global biodiversity assessment teams
US-E3 – Integrate data about distribution, occurrences and functional traits of marine species	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine ecologists • Conservation biologists • Fisheries scientists • Marine protected area managers • Climate change researchers • Biogeographers • Species distribution modelers
US-E4 – Query correlation between marine species observations and fishing boats locations from AIS data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fisheries scientists • Marine policy analysts • Fishing fleet managers • Marine surveillance officers • Fisheries enforcement agencies • Marine spatial planning experts • Fish stock assessment scientists

Use Case	Stakeholders
US-E5 – MSFD - Descriptor 1: Good Environmental Status in relation to biological diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU marine policy officers • Marine biodiversity assessors • Regional seas convention coordinators • Government marine agencies • Marine conservation NGOs

4.3 Competency questions for WoRMS and EurOBIS data

Competency questions are important building blocks of the eXtreme Design methodology we have followed when designing and engineering the ontologies.

Competency questions can be defined as questions posed by users (user centricity), expressed in natural language, whose answers can be obtained by leveraging the capabilities of the ontologies to support those questions.

In the context of ontology design, competency questions play a crucial role in guiding the development and evaluation of the ontology. They serve several purposes:

- *Requirements Elicitation*: Competency questions help identify the key information needs and requirements of users or stakeholders. By articulating the questions users want to ask of the ontology, designers can ensure that the ontology addresses relevant aspects of the domain.
- *Scope Definition*: Competency questions help define the scope and boundaries of the ontology. They clarify what aspects of the domain the ontology should cover and what types of information it should represent.
- *Evaluation Criteria*: Competency questions serve as criteria for evaluating the ontology's effectiveness and completeness. If the ontology can accurately and comprehensively answer the competency questions, it indicates that the ontology adequately represents the domain.
- *Quality Assurance*: Competency questions help assess the quality of the ontology's design and implementation. By verifying that the ontology can answer the intended questions correctly, designers can ensure its accuracy, consistency, and relevance.
- *Iterative Improvement*: Competency questions facilitate iterative refinement and enhancement of the ontology. As new requirements emerge or existing ones change, designers can modify the ontology and evaluate its effectiveness based on the evolving set of competency questions.

Overall, competency questions act as a bridge between the conceptualization of a domain and the development of an ontology, guiding designers in creating ontologies that accurately capture the knowledge and meet the information needs of users.

As for use cases, during the first business workshop we asked participants to formulate questions of their interest based on their experience.

Table 7 lists some of the competency questions that have been identified for the WoRMS data by stakeholders and by VLIZ's domain experts, this latter highlighting relevant data questions also in preparation of the aforementioned meeting.

Table 7: Competency questions for WoRMS data identified during workshops with external and internal stakeholders

Competency question ID	Competency question description
CQ-W1	Where does species XX appear?
CQ-W2	Which species from the Habitat/Bird Directive are on the IUCN Red List?
CQ-W3	Can I surf in the area ZZ? Are there sharks?
CQ-W4	Which alien species are known to occur in the Mediterranean Sea?
CQ-W5	Which is the body size of species XX?
CQ-W6	Who are the owners of the images associated with species XX?
CQ-W7	What are the synonyms for the name YY?
CQ-W8	Which is the aphia identifier for species XX?
CQ-W9	Which are the common names in Italian for species XX?
CQ-W10	Which are all the attributes and traits for species XX with the related sources?
CQ-W11	What are the habitats of species XX?
CQ-W12	Which species are known to be invasive in region ZZ?
CQ-W13	Which species have been discovered in region ZZ?
CQ-W14	What is the type locality of species XX?
CQ-W15	What is the taxonomic classification (e.g., kingdom, phylum, class) of species XX?
CQ-W16	What is the valid/accepted scientific name for species XX?
CQ-W17	What is the conservation status of species XX according to IUCN?
CQ-W18	What are the references/sources cited for the taxonomic information of species XX?

In contrast, Table 8 lists some competency questions that have been identified by stakeholders internal and external aligned with the EurOBIS data. The list of Table 8 is complemented with additional competency questions that have been found when the analysis of the state of the art has been carried out.

Table 8: Competency questions for EurOBIS data collected from internal and external stakeholders

Competency question ID	Competency question description
CQ-E1	Where has the species XX been observed?
CQ-E2	Which (macro)benthic species live in the North Sea at depths between 50-100m?
CQ-E3	What is the maximum and minimum salinity where organisms with DNA sequence homology above x% with this given DNA sequence have been found
CQ-E4	How the abundance of the species XX varied/will vary over time? or according to some abiotic variable (T, salinity...)
CQ-E5	How many individuals of species X in area Y
CQ-E6	What was the average temperature of the North Sea (or any other region R) the last 5 (n) times there was an Orca (species S) spotted there?
CQ-E7	Can I swim in / drink from the waters at X?

<i>Competency question ID</i>	<i>Competency question description</i>
CQ-E8	In a given area, are there any biophysical, chemical hazards (not only sharks :) - e.g., toxic waste, extreme temperatures, biochemical functional genes producing toxics, diseases, microbes, parasites, etc.) I should be aware of?
CQ-E9	How many occurrences of a certain species are there?
CQ-E10	Which is the specific nature of the collected object?
CQ-E11	Which country does an occurrence belong to?
CQ-E12	Which is the biome associated with a specific location?
CQ-E13	Which is the taxonomic classification of the collected object?
CQ-E14	What occurrences exist within a bounding box?
CQ-E15	When has the survey XX happened?
CQ-E16	Which was the temperature of the water when species XX occurred in area YY?
CQ-E17	Which is the name of the vessel that detected the presence of species XX in area YY?
CQ-E18	Given a specific marine region YY, what are all the species (or a specific species XX) observed?

4.4 WoRMS data details

The main types of data managed by WoRMS are the following:

- Taxonomies;
- Distributions;
- Attributes and Traits;
- Specimen (very few and to be further investigated in the future)
- Vernacular names
- Identifiers
- Notes
- Sources
- Images

Table 9 includes the main aspects regarding the WoRMS data that were presented by VLIZ's colleagues during the first thematic workshop on WoRMS. This provides us with a list of possible types of data to be taken into account in a more bottom-up approach when designing ontology modules of the APHIA network.

Table 9: Data aspects to be considered for producing Linked Open Data and developing ontologies

<i>Aspect ID</i>	<i>Aspect description</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
AS1	basics of id, name	Worms does not track taxa but only names. Names are associated with a URN identifier
AS2	resource metadata (license, creator, ...)	-
AS3	taxonomic status	Controlled vocabulary to be considered
AS4	parent by id (taxonomic hierarchy)	-

Aspect ID	Aspect description	Remarks
AS5	names on all levels of the taxonomic tree	-
AS6	geographic distribution	Link to marine regions
AS7	vernacular (alternative names)	Available translated variants Challenge: attribute the association with the authoritative "source"
AS8	source	Link to the authoritative source
AS9	traits / attributes	Secondary reference requires concepts
AS10	media (image/video)	-
AS11	links (other sources)	-
AS12	notes	Free text field. Note types are available
AS13	specimens	Very limited

4.5 EurOBIS data details

The Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) is a global open-access data and information clearing-house on marine biodiversity for science, conservation and sustainable development. EurOBIS functions as the European regional node of the global OBIS network and is hosted by the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) in Belgium.

4.5.1 Overview

As an OBIS node and data provider, EurOBIS is subject to the rules and requirements defined in the OBIS manual²⁵, where the format and contents of data are defined.

Figure 14: Main EurOBIS information elements

²⁵ <https://manual.obis.org/>

As graphically summarised in Figure 14, EurOBIS manages several types of marine biodiversity data; the main types of data managed by EurOBIS are the following:

- **Event Information:** Details about research cruises, sampling stations, sampling activities, collection methods, and protocols used to gather the biological and environmental data, with details about when and where the event or activity took place.
- **Species Occurrence Data:** Georeferenced records of marine species observations, including taxonomic information, spatial coordinates, temporal data, and abundance information when available.
- **Environmental Data:** Physical, chemical, and biological measurements associated with events and species observations, including biotic and abiotic parameters like temperature, salinity, depth, pH, nutrient concentrations, organism characteristics and species biometrics.

Examples of data is also shown in Figure 15 for some of the main identified elements.

Figure 15: Examples of data for some main information elements in EurOBIS

All information managed in EurOBIS directly relies on Darwin Core (DwC): DwC terms correspond to the column names of an EurOBIS dataset and can be grouped according to DwC class type for convenience. Darwin Core Archive²⁶ (DwC-A) is the standard for packaging and publishing biodiversity data using Darwin Core terms. It is the preferred format for publishing data in OBIS. Basically, a Darwin Core Archive contains a number of text files, including data tables formatted as CSV. The conceptual data model of the Darwin Core Archive is a star schema with a single core table, for example containing occurrence records or event records, at the center of the star. Extension tables can optionally be associated with the core table.

²⁶ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/text/>

Figure 16: Main entities in the (Eur)OBIS data model

Specifically, OBIS (and thus EurOBIS) adopts the OBIS-ENV data model [25], which represents an evolution of the traditional OBIS data structure to better accommodate environmental data alongside biological occurrence information. In particular, the OBIS-ENV data model allows overcoming the limitations of the star schema of Darwin Core archive, which prevented associating measurements with the event records as well as with the occurrence records. As intuitively shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17, the tripartite structure (Events, Occurrences and MeasurementsOrFacts) allows OBIS-ENV to capture complex ecological datasets that include hierarchical sampling designs, multiple environmental parameters, and detailed biological observations, providing a robust framework for marine biodiversity and environmental data integration.

Figure 17: OBIS-ENV core entities and relationships

Yet, the data model behind EurOBIS follows the data conceptualisation of Darwin Core and thus suffers from all the limitations highlighted earlier in the state-of-the-art analysis concerning DwC (see Section 3.1).

The current model shows a rather flat structure, a design choice where properties conceptually belonging to distinct entities are directly attached to other entity types. A clear example of this, as previously discussed, is the direct association of "sample size" with the event entity, rather than with the sample itself, which is a separate product produced by a possible sampling event.

4.5.2 Core entities and fields

An EurOBIS dataset represented as a Darwin Core Archive can cover three main entity types: Events, Occurrences and ExtendedMeasurementsOrFacts. Each major entity is then described in terms of a number of attributes that are classified in the OBIS manual as being *(i)* required; *(ii)* strongly recommended; *(iii)* recommended; or *(iv)* optional.

For example, for characterising an event entity (where event can be a survey, a cruise, an observation campaign, a sampling activity, etc.), an identifier and a date are required, as well as the coordinates of the location and a parent identifier if there exists a hierarchy of events. Additional attributes for defining the temporal dimension and size of the sample produced during a sampling event are strongly recommended.

Core entities and their fields are summarised below, with a focus on fields that are *required* or *strongly recommended*.

Event

An Event is an action, process, or set of circumstances occurring at some location during a period of time. The Event entity serves as the foundational unit for organizing sampling activities and represents the temporal and spatial context of data collection. Key Event fields are listed in Figure 18.

Term	OBIS requirements	DwC class
eventID	required	Event
parentEventID	required (if exists)	Event
eventDate	required	Event
year	strongly recommended	Event
month	strongly recommended	Event
eventType	strongly recommended	Event
samplingProtocol	strongly recommended	Event
samplingEffort	strongly recommended	Event
sampleSizeValue	strongly recommended	Event
sampleSizeUnit	strongly recommended	Event
decimalLatitude	required	Location
decimalLongitude	required	Location
coordinatePrecision	strongly recommended	Location
coordinateUncertaintyInMeters	strongly recommended	Location
continent	strongly recommended	Location
locationID	strongly recommended	Location

Figure 18: Key Event fields in (Eur)OBIS

Occurrence

The Occurrence entity allows recording an observation about the existence of an organism at a particular place at a particular time. It thus contains information about individual species observations linked to specific events. Each occurrence record represents the presence or absence of a taxon (identified by its scientific name) at a particular place and time, or in the context of an event. Key Occurrence fields include those listed before for an Event, with the addition of the fields listed in Figure 19.

Term	OBIS requirements	DwC class
occurrenceID	required	Occurrence
occurrenceStatus	required	Occurrence
basisOfRecord	required (if exists)	Record
organismQuantity	strongly recommended	Occurrence
organismQuantityType	strongly recommended	Occurrence
scientificName	required	Taxon
scientificNameID	strongly recommended	Taxon
taxonRank	strongly recommended	Taxon
kingdom	strongly recommended	Taxon
order	strongly recommended	Taxon
genus	strongly recommended	Taxon

Figure 19: Key Occurrence fields in (Eur)OBIS

ExtendedMeasurementOrFact (eMoF)

A measurement or fact is an assertion made in relation to an Event or Occurrence. With this entity it is possible to report a variety of measurements and facts linked to either events or occurrences, such as:

- organism quantifications (e.g. counts, abundance, biomass, % live cover, etc.)
- species biometrics (e.g. body length, weight, etc.)
- facts documenting a specimen (e.g. living/dead, behaviour, invasiveness, etc.)
- abiotic measurements (e.g. temperature, salinity, oxygen, sediment grain size, habitat features)
- facts documenting the sampling activity (e.g. sampling device, sampled area, sampled volume, sieve mesh size).

This is done in a generic way by specifying the property that was observed or measured (e.g., “body length”), the corresponding value (e.g., “25”) with the unit of measure if appropriate (e.g., “cm”). Key ExtendedMeasurementOrFact fields include a reference to the relevant Event and/or Occurrence, plus the fields listed in Figure 20.

Term	OBIS requirements	DwC class
measurementType	strongly recommended	MeasurementOrFact
measurementTypeID	strongly recommended	MeasurementOrFact
measurementValue	strongly recommended	MeasurementOrFact
measurementValueID	strongly recommended	MeasurementOrFact
measurementUnit	strongly recommended	MeasurementOrFact
measurementUnitID	strongly recommended	MeasurementOrFact
samplingProtocol	strongly recommended	Event
samplingEffort	strongly recommended	Event
sampleSizeValue	strongly recommended	Event
sampleSizeUnit	strongly recommended	Event
organismQuantity	strongly recommended	Occurrence
organismQuantityType	strongly recommended	Occurrence

Figure 20: Key ExtendedMeasurementOrFact fields in (Eur)OBIS

5 Ontology design – the MAREGRAPH network

On the basis of the previously described methodology, we designed and developed a first set of ontology modules for WoRMS data that are all connected with other each, thus forming a network of modules we named APHIA. We then extended the network with an additional ontology that is able to express the data stored in the EurOBIS system. This ontology is named Marine Observation and is connected with other ontologies of the APHIA network.

A top-level ontology is used to realise the network, enabling the linking between the different modules and semantic inference.

The modules are dependent on the different types of data that both WoRMS and EurOBIS databases provide to their users. In particular, the current APHIA network consists of four domain ontology modules in addition to the top-level ontology. The EurOBIS cluster consists of one ontology that imports the top-level and uses ontology modules of APHIA network. All the modules are depicted in Figure 21. The grey circles represent our developed ontologies, the white circles are external ontologies we import whilst the light blue circle in is the marine region ontology already published by VLIZ. The arrows in Figure 21 represent `owl:imports` axioms among the ontologies or the re-use (`uses` property) of single elements of other modules/ontologies. In Figure 21 also includes the prefixes of each module or ontology.

Figure 21: The MAREGRAPH network of ontologies

All the ontologies, and their elements, are identified by URIs that have been formed according to the various European and national best practices²⁷. Specifically, the URIs are built according to the following scheme:

```
https://[namespace]/[type]/[concept]/[reference]
```

As shown in Figure 21 in the prefixes box, the chosen namespace is `aphia.org` for the APHIA network and `eurobis.org` for the data coming from EuroBIS. Since we are defining URIs for ontologies, the type chosen is `ns`, following Digital Flanders rules and W3C practice²⁸. The concept represents the name of the ontology and the reference part is the unique identifier of each element of the ontology.

The network's domain ontologies include labels and definitions available in English, Italian, and Dutch, thus enabling multilingualism.

In addition, OWL restrictions; namely, special kinds of class descriptions have been introduced in all the modules. These are anonymous classes, i.e., classes of all individuals that satisfy the specific restrictions (constraints on values and properties). The OWL restrictions allow us to enable semantic inference and provide a view of cardinality constraints that impact on the data quality.

All the ontologies are currently publicly available in the following GitHub repository <https://github.com/MareGraph-EU/assets/tree/main>, where the produced versions are tracked.

The publication on GitHub is the result of a long internal discussion with the data experts. A public review for the development of the APHIA network has been carried out. Unfortunately, despite the communication sent to the community we built over these years of the MAREGRAPH project, no feedback was received, with the exception of a group of Italian researchers working in the Italian LifeWatch node who wanted to harmonise the data on attributes and traits under the form of a common and unique SKOS-based controlled vocabulary.

In the following subsections we describe each module, highlighting some design choices and semantic alignments to external ontologies, if available. Some of these modules, already published when D3.1 was delivered, have been updated. This deliverable introduces those updates. In the case of marine observations, this document describes the new ontology module that has been created to express that type of data.

5.1 Top-level ontology module

As previously introduced, in order to connect all the domain ontology modules, and also define general entities that are independent of the specific fishery domain (e.g., a source, a

²⁷ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre/document/10-rules-persistent-uris>

²⁸ The Italian government generally uses the same scheme to specify URIs; however, the 'type' element chosen is 'onto' when identifying ontologies, in order to have URIs that are as spoken as possible

value, a name, the time) but useful for our modelling needs, we decided to propose the definition of a so-called top-level ontology.

The ontology imports a well-known foundational ontology available in the ontology representation literature; namely, d0 that in turn imports the DOLCE+DnS Ultralite ontology, a simplification of some parts of the DOLCE Lite-Plus library [1]. D0 defines general classes like `Characteristic` represented as the union of other classes expressed in DOLCE+DnS Ultralite ontology.

When importing an entire ontology, the imported ontology is an integral part of the ontological definition being made. In the specific case of the top-level various classes and properties of d0 and thus DOLCE + DnS Ultralite were then used directly or indirectly in the domain ontology modules of the MAREGRAPH network described below.

However, for general modelling needs, further classes and properties were added. In particular, we the classes `top-level:Name`, `top-level:Source`, `top-level:Value`, `top-level:UnitOfMeasure`, `top-level:Identifier`, `top-level:IdentifierType`, `top-level:System` and their related object and data type properties (e.g., `top-level:hasIdentifier`, `top-level:isAssignedBy`, `top-level:hasType`, `top-level:value`, `top-level:hasValue`).

Since the publication of D3.1, the top-level ontology has been further extended in order to model:

- the context associated with a Taxon Name. The context `i(top-level:Context)` is currently represented with the system that provides the data and the license associated with the provider;
- the notion of time, that resulted rather relevant in the context of the EurOBIS data. In particular, a generic `top-level:TemporalEntity` was created then characterised by a set of properties for capturing the notions of year, month and generic time expressed as a string.

5.2 Taxon name ontology module

One of the most important domain ontology modules of the APHIA network is the so-called Taxon name module (preferred prefix `taxon-name`).

During the first half of the project, this module was discussed extensively with the WoRMS database domain experts because it includes critical modelling elements that are necessary to provide consistent semantics. Moreover, this module is the basis for all the other modules described in this deliverable. In fact, it represents the set of taxonomic information that allows for the unambiguous identification of marine species and any changes in classification that occur over time.

In Figure 22 and Figure 23 we illustrate two graphical representations expressed using the Graffoo notation of two main elements of the ontology; namely, the scientific names and all the taxonomic information, and the vernacular names, respectively.

Figure 22: The scientific name and other taxonomic information of the Taxon name ontology module

Figure 23: The vernacular name of the Taxon name ontology module

As reported earlier, the problem of identifying marine species by their names has been widely discussed in the literature. In the WoRMS database, all information on marine species is linked to scientific names because in the relevant publications, from which WoRMS derives its data, only the names are cited to identify the species (set of organisms) that are thus implied. This certainly simplifies database management, but from a semantic point of view, such management creates semantic inconsistencies.

In general, looking at the reality of the domain, the semiotic triangle applies: taxa are things (i.e., referents) to which our concepts (i.e., references) refer and are labelled or symbolised by means of scientific names (see Section 3). This suggests that there should be a clear distinction between things and the symbols used to label them. For example, a picture of a fish represents an organism (a thing), not the name of that organism; therefore, it cannot simply be associated with a scientific name, even though that name is used to refer to the organism.

In the light of these considerations, we propose an ontology module where there exist two classes: a `taxon-name:Taxon` class (concept) that is distinct from the class `taxon-name:TaxonName` that represents the name (symbol, label). Using a class to represent the name of the taxon then allows us to predicate on that name to specify for instance the authorship (`taxon-name:authorship` in Figure 22), the status (`taxon-name:Status` in Figure 22) or other properties. This modelling choice is the same as the one adopted in several semantic-based scientific publications and, specifically, the one proposed by an extension of the well-consolidated SKOS ontology named SKOS-XL (as also represented in Figure 22). In SKOS-XL the Label is a class (`taxon-name:TaxonName rdfs:subClassOf skos-xl:Label`) and the concept is the class from SKOS (`taxon-name:Taxon rdfs:subClassOf skos:Concept`).

Since a taxon may have different types of names other than the scientific one, we introduced in the top-level ontology module a generic abstract class `top-level:Name` that groups all these different types. This modelling choice allows for specifying general properties that may apply to all types of names (i.e., the `taxon-name:denotes` object property that links `top-level:Name` to `taxon-name:Taxon`) In fact, `top-level:Name` is the super class of both `taxon-name:TaxonName` and `taxon-name:VernacularName` (see Figure 23) where the specialisations are marked as disjoint (Figure 23) because if the name is a scientific name it cannot be at the same time a vernacular name. This latter is an informal name used by the general public or within specific communities to refer to an organism. Unlike scientific names, which follow standardised rules, vernacular names can vary regionally or culturally. These names often reflect characteristics, behaviours, appearances, or uses of the organism and can be quite diverse across different languages and regions. These two latter elements are in fact used to characterise the semantic definition of vernacular names and are represented using two properties, `dct:language` and `dct:coverage` in Figure 23.

In addition to the above important modelling part of the ontology, it represents other taxonomic data like the whole taxonomic classification of taxa (through the `taxon-name:Rank` class), any identifier, including the APHIA identifier (i.e., the identifier assigned by the APHIA system – `taxon-name:aphiaID` in Figure 22), associated with the name since in WoRMS this information is pertinent to the scientific name of the species, the relations between the taxon and its name depending on the status of the name (e.g., accepted, unaccepted) – `taxon-name:hasAcceptedName` `taxon-name:hasSynonymName` in Figure 22.

For all key classes of this ontology module `taxon-name:Taxon`, `taxon-name:TaxonName`, `taxon-name:VernacularName` the (scientific) source is captured in order to always maintain the provenance of the information included in scientific publications.

Finally, based on the first LOD produced about taxa and their scientific names, we applied changes in the ontology with respect to the version we introduced in D3.1. These changes can be summarised as follows.

Firstly, the *unaccepted reason* for a taxonomic name is typically a highly variable string, making a simple data type property the most suitable representation for capturing this free-

text information. Secondly, to reflect the taxonomic citation provided by WoRMS for each taxon name, we leveraged the `dct:bibliographicCitation` property. This ensures proper attribution and traceability to original sources. Finally, it was crucial to incorporate contextual information associated with each taxon name, specifically regarding the system data provider (e.g., Fishbase) and the license under which the provider contributes data to the WoRMS system. These comprehensive changes are now fully represented in Figure 22.

5.2.1 Implemented ontology design patterns

This ontology module implements, in the reference domain, a set of general ontology design patterns. The patterns are listed in Table 10 along with the related implementation in the taxon name ontology module.

Table 10: Ontology Design Patterns implemented in the Taxon name ontology module

<i>Name of the ontology design pattern</i>	<i>Taxon name module element</i>
Classification ²⁹	<code>taxon-nameTaxonName top-level:hasStatus</code> <code>taxon-name:Status</code> <code>taxon-name:TaxonName taxon-name:isOfRank taxon-name:Rank</code>
LinnaeanTaxonomy (only partially) ³⁰	<code>taxon-name:Taxon, taxon-name:hasChild, taxon-name:hasParent</code>
Literal Reification ³¹	<code>taxon-name:TaxonName taxon-name:scientificName</code> <code>rdfs:Literal</code>

5.2.2 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

We introduced direct and indirect semantic alignments with external ontologies.

In particular, all classes are aligned with the top-level ontology and thus to DUL/d0 foundational ontology. Moreover, using the PROV-O Web standard, we introduced some lightweight semantic alignments indicating that certain defined classes in the taxon name ontology module are derived from other available ontologies of the domain.

One of the external reference vocabularies for this module is Darwin Core (see Section 3). However, it is worth noting that although the RDF version is mentioned in the documentation, there does not seem to be a specific RDF vocabulary for Darwin Core. There is only a guideline on how to represent linked data with the vocabulary. Despite of this uncertain scenario, URIs for properties and classes are specified in the vocabulary as if describing a real RDF vocabulary; therefore, those URIs have been used to provide semantic alignments however specifically required by VLIZ.

²⁹ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Classification>

³⁰ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:LinnaeanTaxonomy>

³¹ http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Literal_Reification

Table 11: Semantic alignments for the Taxon name ontology module

<i>Taxon name module element</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment</i>	<i>External ontology</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment type</i>
taxon-name:Taxon	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept prov:wasDerivedFrom dwc:Taxon prov:wasDerivedFrom schema:Taxon	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology Darwin Core Vocabulary Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:TaxonName	subClassOf skos-xl:Label prov:wasDerivedFrom openbiodiv:LatinName prov:wasDerivedFrom bioschemas:TaxonName	SKOS-XL ontology OpenBiodiv-O ontology Bioschemas.org	indirect
taxon-name:VernacularName	prov:wasDerivedFrom openbiodiv:VernacularName	OpenBiodiv-O ontology	indirect
taxon-name:Status	subClassOf skos:Concept subClassOf dul:Concept	SKOS ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
taxon-name:Rank	subClassOf skos:Concept subClassOf dul:Concept	SKOS ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
taxon-name:UnacceptedReason	subClassOf skos:Concept subClassOf dul:Concept	SKOS ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
dct:LinguisticSystem	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:Location	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:source	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:coverage	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:language	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct

<i>Taxon name module element</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment</i>	<i>External ontology</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment type</i>
taxon-name:hasChild	skos:narrower	SKOS ontology	indirect
taxon-name:hasParent	skos:broader	SKOS ontology	indirect
taxon-name:aphiaID	dwc:scientificNameID	Darwin Core vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:authorship	dwc:scientificNameAuthorship	Darwin Core vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:fullScientificName	dwc:scientificName skos-xl:literalForm	Darwin Core vocabulary SKOS-XL vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:scientificName	skos-xl:literalForm	SKOS-XL vocabulary	indirect
taxon-name:vernacularName	dwc:vernacularName skos-xl:literalForm	Darwin Core vocabulary SKOS-XL vocabulary	indirect

All the other object properties are aligned with the top-level ontology and thus to DUL/d0 foundational ontologies.

5.3 Distribution ontology module

The distribution ontology (preferred prefix: `td`) module has been developed to represent all the geographical elements that allow one to localise the marine species in marine regions, providing context information for the species with respect to their locations.

The graphical representation using the Graffoo notation is illustrated in Figure 24.

Figure 24: The Distribution ontology module

From the proposed modelling, we observe that a `taxon-name:Taxon` can be directed linked to a marine region (`mr:MRGeoObject`). This latter class of the ontology is defined within the related Marine Regions Gazetteer ontology, which was already available before the official start of the MAREGRAPH project. However, during the design of the distribution module we noticed the lack of the definition of the property `mr:occursIn` within the ontology source code, despite its description was present in related documentation. This discrepancy will bring us to modify the Marine Regions Gazetteer ontology in the context of the MAREGRAPH project, to reflect the presence of this important property required for defining the distribution.

In addition to the direct link to a Marine Region, the ontology includes the representation of a general concept of Distribution (the class `td:Distribution` in Figure 24) that is an overall situation that puts together many elements that characterise the geographical distribution of marine species. In essence, from a technical point of view, it represents an n-ary relationship.

In particular, based on WoRMS data, the distribution defines not only the area (the `td:hasArea` object property of Figure 24 that connects to a Marine Region) but also the geometry (`locn:Geometry`), the origin of the species (the `td:Origin` class), the invasiveness information (the `td:Invasiveness` class); that is, the propensity of an introduced species to invade a recipient ecosystem, the type of occurrence (the `td:Occurrence` class); that is, the presence of species at locations of interest, the (scientific) source (the `top-level:Source` class) from which all the distribution details are derived, whether it is typed (the `td:isTypeLocality` data type property) or not and any other note (the `skos:note` data type property), written in the form of a string, for describing the distribution.

It is important to notice that most of the classes connected to the Distribution class can be modelled as controlled vocabularies; that is, the individuals of all those classes can be the

concepts of SKOS-based controlled vocabularies to be built according to the terminology provided by the marine specie website³².

We engaged in an internal discussion regarding the optimal representation of marine regions in relation to taxa. The debate centered on whether to maintain a direct link between a taxon and its associated Marine Region, or to rely solely on the "Distribution" reification, which encapsulates a broader set of contextual concepts.

While acknowledging the significant value of the "Distribution" concept in providing comprehensive contextual information about the locations pertinent to a taxon, it has been decided to also retaining a direct property linking a taxon to its Marine Region. This direct link offers an added value by simplifying queries for end-users who are solely interested in retrieving the Marine Region for a given taxon, without needing to navigate through the more complex "Distribution" reification. This dual approach ensures both rich contextualization and straightforward accessibility for different querying needs. Moreover, this choice in the conceptual model does not imply that these two modelling possibilities will be adopted during the actual data materialization; rather, both approaches can be simultaneously implemented to cater to diverse data access and querying requirements, or just one of the two.

In the light of these considerations, no specific changes with respect to the version published in D3.1 have been applied.

5.3.1 Implemented ontology design patterns

The main ontology design patterns that has been used in this ontology module are the situation pattern³³, that has been implemented through the class `td:Distribution` for the `taxon-name:Taxon`, and the place pattern³⁴ that is implemented through the properties `mr:occursIn` and `td:hasArea` that link the taxon and its distribution, respectively, to a place.

5.3.2 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

The design of the distribution module is characterised by preliminary identified direct and indirect semantic alignments to external ontologies. The following Table 12 lists those alignments.

³² <https://www.marinespecies.org/introduced/terminology.php>

³³ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Situation>

³⁴ <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/cp/owl/place.owl>

Table 12: Semantic alignments for the Distribution ontology module

<i>Distribution module element</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment</i>	<i>External ontology</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment type</i>
td:Distribution	subClassOf dul:Situation	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
td:Origin	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology	indirect
td:Invasiveness	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology	indirect
td:Occurrence	subClassOf dul:Concept subClassOf skos:Concept	DUL Foundational ontology SKOS ontology	indirect
locn:geometry	-	Core Location vocabulary	direct
skos:note	-	SKOS ontology	direct
dct:source	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
td:hasArea	subPropertyOf dwc:locality subPropertyOf dul:hasLocation	Darwin Core vocabulary DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
td:hasOccurrence	subPropertyOf dwc:occurrenceStatus subPropertyOf dul:isAssociatedWith	Darwin Core vocabulary DUL Foundational ontology	indirect

All the rest of the object properties are aligned with the DUL foundational ontology used in the top-level ontology module of the APHIA network.

5.4 Media ontology module

The media ontology (preferred prefix: `media`) module has been developed to represent all the media resources (e.g., video, image) that can be associated with marine species.

The graphical representation using the Graffoo notation is illustrated in Figure 25.

Figure 25: The Media ontology module

For this ontology we also produced the UML diagram, according to our methodology. The UML class diagram, with the indication of the cardinalities of the properties, is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: UML diagram for the media ontology module

In general, the media module follows the modelling pattern that has been proposed in schema.org. Therefore, the `taxon-name:Taxon` is the subject (the `media:isSubjectOf` object property) of a generic media object (the abstract class

`media:MediaObject` in Figure 25 and Figure 26). The object can be instantiated with two types named `media:ImageObject` and `media:VideoObject` representing images and videos resources, respectively. Note that these two classes are defined as disjoint, meaning that instances of type `media:ImageObject` cannot be at the same time instances of `media:VideoObject`. The proposed modelling is sufficiently general to accommodate the introduction in the future of other types of media objects like audio for instance.

For describing those types of objects a set of properties of the `media:MediaObject` class has been identified in order to represent:

- the format of the media object (the object property `dct:format` connected to the class `dct:MediaTypeObject`);
- the license associated with the media object (the object property `dct:license` connected to the class `dct:LisenceDocument`);
- the title and description if available of the media object (`dct:title` and `dct:description` data type properties);
- the person or organization (i.e., agents) that owns rights on the media object (`dct:rightsholder` connected to the class `dct:Agent`)

The properties included in the graphical representation of the module are the most recurrent and important ones. Additional properties can be specified in the data when required (e.g., size, URL of the media resource) thanks to the semantic alignment of the `media:MediaObject` class to the related Schema.org class (see Section 5.4.1). To this end, it is worth pointing out that, following other European practices, we have decided to indirectly align our ontological module with Schema.org in order to be partially independent of that model, thus guaranteeing a certain degree of sustainability of our semantic definition over time. Schema.org is a data model proposed by a private US company that could decide, at any time, to discontinue maintenance of the model or modify currently defined elements according to its own specific market needs. However, despite these motivations for indirect alignment, this modelling choice allows us to use Schema.org in the LOD anyway, borrowing certain properties from it only when necessary, according to data representation needs.

In contrast, this module uses directly many properties of Dublin Core. Dublin Core is an ISO standard whose definition follows a typically long standardization programme. This guarantees the stability of the model over time, and in turn the sustainability of our semantics that directly reuse it.

No specific changes have been applied since the publication of the module in D3.1,

5.4.1 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

The following Table 13 lists the preliminary semantic alignments of the media ontology module.

Table 13: Semantic alignments for the Media module

Media module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
media:MediaObject	subClassOf schema:MediaObject	Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
media:ImageObject	subClassOf schema:ImageObject	Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
media:VideoObject	subClassOf schema:VideoObject	Schema.org vocabulary	indirect
dct:Agent	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:LicenseDocument	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:MediaTypeOrExtent	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
dct:rightsHolder dct:title dct:description dct:license dct:format dct:subject	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct

5.5 Attribute and trait ontology module

The attribute and trait ontology (preferred prefix: `tat`) module has been developed to represent all the data regarding attributes and traits of marine species and their context information, which may not even be known a priori and extended in the future.

Attributes are qualities or characteristics whereby a taxon can be distinguished and are typically associated with categorical values. In contrast, traits are any measurable or observable characteristics of an organism. In the WoRMS database, at the time being, there is only one documented trait for marine species; that is, the 'body size'.

The graphical representation using the Graffoo notation of the ontology module is illustrated in Figure 27.

Figure 27: The Attribute-trait ontology module

In the proposed modelling despite the environment is considered an attribute of a taxon, it has been modelled in a different way with respect to other attributes/traits. In fact, the habitat or environment is an important element that has its own standalone identity in many vocabularies available in the literature. Therefore, it has been decided to make it evident in the modelling through the definition of a class named `taxon:Environment` which is linked to the taxon through the object property `taxon:hasHabitat`, a terminology widely recognised in the fishery domain. The individuals of the `taxon:Environment` class can be the concepts of a specific SKOS-based controlled vocabulary to be created to represent the different habitats of the marine species (e.g., marine, freshwater).

The rest of the attributes and traits included in the WoRMS database were modelled with a highly flexible modelling scheme to accommodate future evolutions on the management and content of this type of data in the WoRMS system. In essence, the proposed modelling allows one to introduce additional traits and attributes, and further extra context information for them, without repeatedly changing the ontology with each new evolution/extension.

Since, the attributes and traits are used to *describe* the qualities and characteristics of a taxon, we introduced the class `taxon:TaxonDescription` for this purpose. As in the case of the Distribution class in the distribution ontology module, the `taxon:TaxonDescription` is a situation description that allows one to put together, for a given `taxon-name:Taxon`, different elements:

1. the trait or attribute itself (the class `taxon:TaxonCharacteristic` then specialised in `taxon:Trait` and `taxon:Attribute` classes in Figure 27);
2. the value the attribute or trait assumes (the class `top-level:Value`), be it categorial or quantitative value (in the latter case a `top-level:UnitOfMeasure` is specified);
3. an extra specification (the class `taxon:SpecificationContext`) that combines additional parameters (`dul:Parameter`), and their values (the class `top-`

level:Value) to connote the attributes and traits of the taxon description (examples of specification contexts are: sex, life stage and their permitted values);

4. the (scientific) source (the class `top-level:Source` in Figure 27) from which the data regarding the qualities and characteristics of a taxon was derived.

In domain literature, attributes and traits are well-identified in thesauri (e.g., <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/ontologies/ZOOPLANKTRAITS>) or, in general, in controlled vocabularies of the fishery domain. To this end, it is notable the high interest of some people of the MAREGRAPH co-creation programme, working in the context of the LifeWatch project, to create together with the partners of the project consortium a more comprehensive controlled vocabulary on trait/attribute also using the data coming from the WoRMS database. To achieve this objective, in the ontology we specified a strong semantic alignment towards concepts of these thesauri (see Section 5.5.2). In general, the individuals of the classes `tat:Attribute`, `tat:Trait` and `tat:Environment` can be used to create SKOS-based controlled vocabularies based on the data used in WoRMS.

After publication of D3.1, some discussions raised regarding the possibility to specify hierarchies for attributes and traits and hierarchies for specific context parameters. To this end, two specific properties `tat:isSubSpecificationContextOf` and `tat:isSubTaxonCharacteristicOf` have been introduced to possibly deal with these more articulated scenarios.

5.5.1 Implemented ontology design patterns

This ontology module implements, in the reference domain, a set of general ontology design patterns. The patterns are listed in Table 14 along with the related implementation in the attribute-trait ontology module.

Table 14: Ontology Design Patterns implemented in the Attribute-trait ontology module

<i>Name of the ontology design pattern</i>	<i>Attribute-trait module element</i>
Classification ³⁵	<code>tat:TaxonCharacteristic top-level:hasType top-level:Type</code>
Description ³⁶	<code>tat:TaxonDescription</code>
Species Habitat ³⁷	<code>taxon-name:Taxon tat:hasHabitat tat:Environment</code>
Region ³⁸	<code>tat:TaxonDescription top-level:hasValue top-level:Value</code>

³⁵ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Classification>

³⁶ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Description>

³⁷ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:SpeciesHabitat>

³⁸ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Region>

5.5.2 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

As in the other ontology modules, we introduced direct and indirect semantic alignments with external ontologies. Specifically, all the main classes of the module, as illustrated in Figure 27, are aligned with the top-level ontology that in turn directly reuses DUL Foundational ontology (for example, the class `TaxonDescription` is `subClassOf dul:Description`). In the specific case of parameters of the specification context entity we introduced, we reuse directly the class `dul:Parameter` defined in DUL.

In terms of properties, all object properties are aligned with the properties of the top-level ontology, directly reusing the object properties of DUL. The only exceptions are the source from which we derive taxon trait and attribute data and the additional notes, modelled as strings, used to enrich the description of taxon traits/attributes. In these cases, we directly re-use the `dct:source` property of the ISO Dublin Core standard and `skos:note` of the SKOS ontology Web standard, respectively, as was done in the previously described ontology modules of the APHIA network.

Each single alignment currently included in the ontology module is listed in the following Table 15.

Table 15: Semantic alignments for Attribute-trait ontology module

<i>Attribute-trait module element</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment</i>	<i>External ontology</i>	<i>Semantic Alignment type</i>
<code>tat:TaxonDescription</code>	<code>subClassOf dul:Description</code>	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
<code>tat:TaxonCharacteristic</code>	<code>subClassOf dul:Characteristic</code>	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
<code>tat:SpecificationContext</code>	<code>subClassOf dul:Description</code>	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
<code>tat:Environment</code>	<code>subClassOf skos:Concept</code> <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_01000739></code>	SKOS ontology ENVO ontology (OBO foundry)	indirect
<code>tat:Attribute</code>	<code>subClassOf skos:Concept</code>	SKOS ontology	indirect
<code>tat:Trait</code>	<code>subClassOf skos:Concept</code> <code>equivalentClass <https://kos.lifewatch.eu/thesauri/fishtraits/c_4></code>	SKOS ontology LifeWatch Fish Traits Thesaurus	indirect
<code>dul:Parameter</code>	-	DUL Foundational ontology	direct

Attribute-trait module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
skos:note	-	SKOS ontology	direct
dct:source	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
tat:definesParameter	dul:defines	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
tat:hasAdditionalDescription	dul:isDescribedBy	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
tat:hasExtraSpecification	dul:isRelatedToDescription	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
tat:hasTaxonCharacteristic	dul:defines	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
tat:hasHabitat	dul:isAssociatedWith	DUL Foundational ontology	indirect

5.6 Marine Observation ontology module

While the previous modules were related to the WoRMS database, the Marine Observation ontology (preferred prefix `marine-observation`) has been created to deal with the EurOBIS data. Therefore, the URI of the ontology is different in the namespace with respect to the previous modules since it uses `eurobis.org`.

As previously detailed, the EurOBIS data model, at its foundation, leverages Darwin Core (DwC) classes and properties. This means that data within EurOBIS is structured and managed in a way that aligns with that standard de-facto, and it is typically exchanged using the Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A) format. The DwC-A is essentially a package that bundles together species occurrence data, taxonomic information, event data, measurements or facts data and associated metadata, making it easier to share large biodiversity datasets. This alignment ensures a degree of compatibility with other biodiversity data portals worldwide, such as GBIF.

Furthermore, the design of EurOBIS ensures that all entities and fields within its datasets can be represented as RDF using Darwin Core's terms as defined in the Darwin Core RDF guide³⁹. This is a step towards making EurOBIS data part of the Linked Open Data (LOD) cloud, allowing for semantic interoperability and machine-readability of the data. By transforming the tabular or relational DwC-A structure into RDF triples, the data becomes more amenable to semantic querying and integration with other knowledge graphs.

³⁹ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/rdf/>

However, a significant challenge arises from the nature of Darwin Core itself. While popular and practical, Darwin Core does not define a formal ontology, and the semantics of some elements are underspecified. This lack of formal ontological rigor means that the precise meaning and relationships between certain terms are not always explicitly defined in a way that machines can fully interpret. This underspecification occurs both in the conceptual model and, consequently, in how the data is represented in RDF. For example, a common issue is the use of `dct:relation` (from Dublin Core) as a generic, “catch-all” property to link various entities. While convenient, this broad property with no specific semantics conveyed can obscure specific relationships, making it harder to precisely link, for instance, a `dwc:MeasurementOrFact` to a specific `dwc:Occurrence`. The lack of a more precise predicate makes complex reasoning about these relationships difficult.

A further issue is the flat modelling approach adopted by DwC where some attributes, as already discussed, are related to classes that are not properly described by those properties.

In addition to these limitations, the sheer breadth of data collected in EurOBIS is substantial; records in EurOBIS datasets can utilise over 150 terms from Darwin Core, potentially exceeding 200 if the DNA extension is considered. This vast array of terms, while demonstrating the richness of the data, also presents a challenge for full ontological coverage. Attempting to provide a complete ontological definition for every single possible Darwin Core term, not always materialised in the data (bottom-up approach) and its numerous extensions is an enormous undertaking and beyond the scope of our current project’s objectives. Such an endeavour would require significant resources and community consensus, which are not always feasible within a specific project's timeline.

Therefore, our strategy for releasing EurOBIS data as Linked Open Data (LOD) adopts a pragmatic approach. Rather than pursuing a complete ontological axiomatization of every Darwin Core (DwC) term we prioritise developing a semantic model that focuses on the core classes and properties. Specifically, this includes those elements designated as ‘required’ or ‘strongly recommended’ in the Darwin Core Term Checklist, as tailored for OBIS contributions in the OBIS manual⁴⁰. This targeted focus ensures that the most critical and frequently used data elements possess rich and explicit semantic coverage.

This core semantic model is also designed to have connections to existing Aphia ontology modules (in particular referring to the taxonomic names managed by WoRMS) and the MarineRegions Ontology. By linking to these ontologies we developed, we leverage existing semantic infrastructure for concepts like taxon names and geographical regions, avoiding redundant modelling and enhancing interoperability with these authoritative sources.

Finally, to achieve comprehensive coverage without over-engineering, our strategy is to use established Ontology Design Patterns, aiming for a robust semantic specification and then extend Darwin Core classes where necessary and “fall back” to `dwc:` or `dwciri:` properties for full coverage. This means that for core concepts where a more precise semantic representation is beneficial, we might create new classes or properties that build upon or refine Darwin Core elements. However, for less critical or highly specialised terms, it is possible to use the standard Darwin Core properties (prefixed `dwc:` and `dwciri:`) in our

⁴⁰ <https://manual.obis.org/>

RDF representation. This hybrid approach ensures that all existing data can be materialised as LOD while prioritizing semantic richness for the most impactful and frequently used concepts, balancing practicality with precision for the effective dissemination and exploitation of EurOBIS data.

With this strategy in mind, Figure 28 illustrates the graphical representation using Graffoo of the Marine Observation module.

Figure 28: The Marine Observation ontology module

The main classes shown in Figure 28 are:

- the `marine-observation:BioEvent` which is the entity that represents events occurring in a specific location at a time in the context of the biodiversity domain. Events can be organised in a hierarchy through the use of the property `marine-observation:isSubEventOf`. This property has been introduced in order to meet specific feedback from relevant stakeholders attending the thematic workshop we organised to present the preliminary version of this model for EurOBIS data;
- the `marine-observation:MarineObservation` which is a `BioEvent` and it is further specialised in occurrences of organisms (`marine-observation:OrganismOccurrence`) and assertions (`marine-observation:Assertion`) related to abiotic and biotic factors;
- the `marine-observation:Sampling` to be used in conjunction with the class `marine-observation:Sample` which indicates a specific type of `BioEvent` related to the sampling activity that leads to the production of a sample with its characteristics

- the `marine-observation:MonitoringFacility` which represents the platform such a `marine-observation:Vessel` that makes the specific Observation in the marine context;
- the `marine-observation:OrganismOccurrence` which is the specialisation of the marine observation. It is one of the most important classes of the ontology since it is used to represent the observation of the presence/or absence (through the mandatory `marine-observation:OccurrenceStatus` property) of an organism in a location during a specific time period. The organism is linked to the scientific name of its Taxon. This is one of the most significant connections between the WoRMS-based semantic assets and EurOBIS-based ontology;
- the `marine-observation:Assertion` which is the specialisation of the marine observation. It is a specific type of observation and then bioevent through which assertion about abiotic and biotic properties can be registered.

The class `marine-observation:MarineObservation` is a specific type of reification (it represents an n-ary relationship) that brings together different elements; that is, the specific `marine-observation:ObservableProperty` (that can be treated using specific controlled vocabularies also defined in the context of BODC - British Oceanographic Data Centre), the `marine-observation:BioFeatureOfInterest` for which the property is observed and the result of the observation (`marine-observation:ObservationValue`).

The ontology incorporates usage notes for certain classes and properties, expressed using the SKOS property `skos:usageNote`. These notes serve a purpose: they explicitly detail how to correctly apply the ontology's elements in relation to the original EurOBIS conceptual model. This clear guidance streamlines the process of materializing EurOBIS data, facilitating its transformation and integration through the proposed ontology module.

5.6.1 Implemented ontology design patterns

This ontology module implements, in the reference domain, a set of general ontology design patterns. The patterns are listed in Table 16 along with the related implementation in the marine observation ontology module.

Table 16: Ontology design patterns for the marine observation ontology

<i>Name of the ontology design pattern</i>	<i>Marine observation module element</i>
Classification ⁴¹	<code>marine-observation:MarineObservation</code> <code>marine-observation:ObservableProperty</code>

⁴¹ <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Classification>

Name of the ontology design pattern	Marine observation module element
Observation & Measurement	marine-observation:MarineObservation marine-observation:ObservableProperty marine-observation:BioFeatureOfInterest marine-observation:ObservationValue
Location	marine-observation:occursIn

5.6.2 Semantic alignments to external ontologies

In this section, we introduced direct and indirect semantic alignments with external ontologies. Specifically, all the main classes of the module, as illustrated in Figure 28 are aligned with the top-level ontology that in turn directly reuses DUL Foundation ontology (for example, the class `BioEvent` is `subClassOf dul:Event`) and with other classes of external data models, in particular Darwin Core (i.e., the class `OrganismOccurrence` is `subClassOf dwc:Occurrence`).

In terms of properties, all object properties are aligned with the properties of the top-level ontology, directly reusing the object properties of DUL and with properties of external data models.

Each single alignment currently included in the ontology module is listed in the following Table 17.

Table 17: Semantic alignments with external ontologies for marine observation ontology

Marine observation module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
marine-observation:BioEvent	subClassOf dul:Event dwc:Event bigeonto:BioEvent	DUL Foundational ontology Darwin Core BiGe-Onto	indirect
marine-observation:Assessment	subClassOf dwc:MeasurementOrFact	Darwin Core	indirect
marine-observation:BioFeatureOfInterest	subClassOf sosa:FeatureOfInterest	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:MarineObservation	subClassOf sosa:Observation	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect

Marine observation module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
marine-observation:OrganismOccurrence	subClassOf dwc:Occurrence	Darwin Core	indirect
Marine-observation:OccurrenceBasis	subClassOf skos:Concept	SKOS ontology	indirect
dul:Method	-	DUL Foundational ontology	direct
marine-observation:ObservableProperty	subClassOf skos:Concept sosa:ObservableProperty dul:Quality	SKOS ontology SSN/SOA ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
marine-observation:MonitoringFacility	subClassOf sosa:Platform dul:Object	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:Sampling	subClassOf sosa:Sampling	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:Sample	subClassOf sosa:Sample dwc:MaterialSample	SSN/SOSA ontology Darwin Core	indirect
marine-observation:ObservationValue	subClassOf sosa:Result dul:Region or dul:Object	SSN/SOSA ontology DUL Foundational ontology	indirect
dct:date dct:identifier	-	Dublin Core vocabulary	direct
marine-observation:continentInString	dwc:continent	Darwin Core	indirect
marine-observation:maximumDepthInMeters	dwc: maximumDepthInMeters	Darwin Core	indirect
marine-observation:minimumDepthInMeters	dwc: minimumDepthInMeters	Darwin Core	indirect
marine-observation:samp	dwc:samplingProtocol	Darwin Core	indirect

Marine observation module element	Semantic Alignment	External ontology	Semantic Alignment type
lingProtocolInString			
marine-observation:samplingEffort	dwc:samplingEffort	Darwin Core	indirect
marine-observation:produces	sosa:hasResult	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:usesMethod	sosa:usedProcedure	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:hasBioFeatureOfInterest	sosa:hasFeatureOfInterest	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:hasObservableProperty	sosa:hasObservableProperty	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:hasObservationValue	sosa:hasResult	SSN/SOSA ontology	indirect
marine-observation:hasOccurredInHabitat	dwc:habitat	Darwin Core	indirect
marine-observation:hasOccurrenceStatus	dwc: occurrenceStatus	Darwin Core	indirect

6 How to use the ontologies with real data: small examples

In order to highlight possible critical paths in the creation of LOD using the ontologies previously discussed, we tried to produce so-called reference examples on how to apply the ontologies to real data from WoRMS and EurOBIS.

6.1 Examples of real data from WoRMS

The most critical element is represented by the URI for the Taxon concept. Although from a semantic point of view, the distinction between Taxon and Taxon Name is fundamental to guarantee a certain degree of semantic integrity and consistency, and offered in all existing semantic data models of the reference literature, how to identify a Taxon seems still a challenging task. In the domain, in fact it is not easy to assign a unique identifier for the Taxon (a set of organisms), due to a lack of common agreement on that identification among domain scientists.

A possible solution is to use blank nodes that are nested within the Taxon Name entity to which the APHIA identifier can be assigned and used for creating URIs of the Taxon Name entities.

Blank nodes in general are discouraged in the Linked Open Data world, where the first rule is to provide URIs for everything of the domain being described⁴². Blank nodes can in fact introduce issues in the data querying and management [9]. Despite these observations, we reached an internal consensus to use them in the data as the only solution to face a generalised problem still undefined regarding how to identify Taxon.

In this section we provide a few examples on the reference implementation dataset that we produced from WoRMS data, and that can be used to guide the overall LOD transformation process as described in WP5.

Figure 29 illustrates the example of use of the Taxon Name ontology module to describe the marine species *Scophthalmus maximus*.

⁴² <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

```

# Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758) - Accepted
<https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/127149> a taxon-name:TaxonName , skos-xl:Label ;
  rdfs:label "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  taxon-name:aphiaID "127149" ;
  dwc:scientificNameID "127149" ;
  taxon-name:scientificName "Scophthalmus maximus" ;
  taxon-name:authorship "(Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  dwc:scientificNameAuthorship "(Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  taxon-name:fullScientificName "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  skos-xl:literalForm "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  dwc:scientificName "Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758)" ;
  taxon-name:hasStatus <https://aphia.org/id/taxonomic-status/accepted> ;
  taxon-name:isOfRank <https://aphia.org/id/rank/species> ;
  foaf:depiction <https://images.marinespecies.org/thumbs/3558_scophthalmus-maximus-linnaeus-1758.jpg?w=700.> ;
  dwc:taxonRank <https://aphia.org/id/rank/species> ;
  dct:source <https://www.doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.542> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/260563> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/98466> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/61331> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/publication/70441> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/dataset/17> ,
    <https://marineinfo.org/id/dataset/42> ,
    <https://www.doi.org/10.1111/raq.12052> ,
    <https://www.doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02745-4> ;
  taxon-name:hasSynonym <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/1544773> ;
  taxon-name:denotes _:b0 ;
  top-level:hasIdentifier <https://aphia.org/id/identifier/fishbase-1348> ;
  rdfs:seeAlso <http://www.fishbase.org/Summary/SpeciesSummary.php?id=1348> ,
    <http://apiv3.iucnredlist.org/api/v3/taxonredirect/198731> ,
    <http://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=172748> ,
    <https://www.boldsystems.org/index.php/Taxbrowser_Taxonpage?taxid=78405> .

```

Figure 29: Example of use of Taxon Name ontology module and its semantic alignments with real data

In Figure 29 there is an instance of the Taxon Name entity, whose URI follows the policy described in Section 5 and the APHIA identifier is used as the reference part of the URI⁴³.

In the example above, we also materialise the semantic alignments to SKOS-XL ontology, we import and extend, and to the Darwin Core model through properties like `dwc:scientificName`, `dwc:scientificNameID`, etc.

As it can be noticed, the property `taxon-name:denotes` points to something identified by `_:b0` which is a convention to refer to blank nodes. That property links the Taxon Name with the Taxon entity, this latter defined in Figure 30.

⁴³ We remind here that WoRMS is a database of only names; therefore, it is structured so that all the information is attached to names.

```

_:b0 a taxon-name:Taxon , skos:Concept ;
taxon-name:hasAcceptedName <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/127149> ;
tat:hasHabitat <https://aphia.org/id/environment/marine> ,
..... <https://aphia.org/id/environment/brackish> ;
taxon-name:hasSynonymName <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/1544773> ;
media:isSubjectOf <https://aphia.org/id/image/3558> ;
td:hasDistribution <https://aphia.org/id/distribution/1431356> ;
taxon-name:isDenotedBy <https://aphia.org/id/vernacular-name/3136> ,
..... <https://aphia.org/id/vernacular-name/14224> ;
skos:closeMatch <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q217329> ;
taxon-name:hasParent _:b1 .

_:b1 a taxon-name:Taxon , skos:Concept ;
..... taxon-name:hasAcceptedName <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/126124> .

```

Figure 30: Taxon materialisation using the Taxon Name and other ontology modules

In Figure 30 we define a blank node that is a `taxon-name:Taxon` that has its `acceptedName` linked to the URI presented in Figure 29 and a set of other information that is connected with the Taxon concept. In particular, the example illustrates how to specify an attribute, which is the habitat or environment, vernacular names and the distribution, this latter represented in RDF and depicted in Figure 31.

Please note that in order to create the taxonomic hierarchy between Taxon we use the `taxon-name:hasParent` property that in turn links to another blank node `_:b1` representing another taxon (as shown in Figure 30) with its own accepted name.

Finally, Figure 31 depicts the materialisation of the distribution of the marine species *Scophthalmus maximus*.

```

<https://aphia.org/id/distribution/1431356> a td:Distribution ;
  rdfs:label "Distribution for Scophthalmus maximus (Linnaeus, 1758) - Chinese part of the Yellow Sea"@en ;
  td:isDistributionOf [
    a taxon-name:Taxon , skos:Concept ;
    taxon-name:isDenotedBy <https://aphia.org/id/taxon-name/127149> .
  ] ;
  td:hasArea <http://marineregions.org/mrgid/25469> ;
  dwc:locality <http://marineregions.org/mrgid/25469> ;
  td:hasOrigin <https://aphia.org/id/origin/alien> ;
  td:hasInvasiveness <https://aphia.org/id/invasiveness/not-specified> ;
  td:hasOccurrence <https://aphia.org/id/occurrence/established> ;
  dct:source <https://www.doi.org/10.3391/ai.2017.12.1.11> .

<https://aphia.org/id/origin/alien> a skos:Concept, td:Origin ;
  skos:prefLabel "Alien"@en ;
  rdfs:label "Alien"@en ;
  skos:definition "Species introduced by man into places out of their natural range of distribution"@en .

<https://aphia.org/id/invasiveness/not-specified> a skos:Concept, td:Invasiveness ;
  skos:prefLabel "Not specified"@en ;
  rdfs:label "Not specified"@en ;
  skos:definition "A species whose 'invasiveness' has not been specified in its introduced range. The species is known to be invasive."@en .

<https://aphia.org/id/occurrence/established> a skos:Concept, td:Occurrence ;
  skos:prefLabel "Established"@en ;
  rdfs:label "Established"@en ;
  skos:definition "Species that have become established in their introduced range"@en .

```

Figure 31: Example of materialisation of data on species distribution

As shown in the Figure above, the distribution is identified by a URI where an identifier for distributions have been used. It is linked to the taxon (blank node) denoted by an accepted name and put together various elements of the distribution like the Origin, the Invasiveness, the Occurrence, materialised as SKOS controlled vocabularies (they are instances of `skos:Concept` in Figure 31). The example shows also the use of the marine regions linked open data through the property `hasArea`.

6.2 Examples of real data from EurOBIS

As for the case of WoRMS, in the following we provide illustrative examples that show how the ontology module for marine observations (Section 5.6) can be used to represent data from EurOBIS as RDF using the LOD paradigm.

To this end, we use real-world data from one of the datasets managed by EuroBIS, in particular dataset “Polish Arctic Marine Programme” (<https://doi.org/10.14284/183>). For each of the core entities (Event, Occurrence and ExtendedMeasurementOrFact) we summarise in tabular format one or more records, and we provide the corresponding RDF representation (in Turtle syntax).

eventID	hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812
eventDate	2002-07
year	2002
month	7
decimalLatitude	76.98043
decimalLongitude	15.4356
locality	Hornsund, Spitsbergen_A 2/Greenland Sea
locationID	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C16/current/05/
minimumDepthInMeters	147
maximumDepthInMeters	147

Figure 32: Example of an Event record from EurOBIS

In particular, Figure 33 shows an example of LOD data for the `BioEvent` class and its temporal entity and location, reflecting the data in Figure 32.

```
# Event
<https://eurobis.org/id/event/243_hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812>
  a marine-observation:BioEvent , dwc:Event , marine-observation:Sampling ;
  rdfs:label "Event hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812 on 2002-07 at (76.98043 15.4356)"@en ;
  dct:identifier "hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812" ;
  dct:date "2002-07"^^xsd:gYearMonth ;
  dwc:eventDate "2002-07"^^xsd:gYearMonth ;
  dwc:year "2002"^^xsd:gYear ;
  dwc:month "7"^^xsd:integer ;
  top-level:hasTemporalEntity <https://eurobis.org/id/temporal-entity/2002-07> ;
  marine-observation:occursIn <https://eurobis.org/id/location/76.98043-15.4356> ;
  marine-observation:produces <https://eurobis.org/id/sample/243_hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812> .

# Temporal entity
<https://eurobis.org/id/temporal-entity/2002-07>
  a top-level:TemporalEntity ;
  rdfs:label "2002-07" ;
  top-level:year "2002"^^xsd:gYear ;
  top-level:month "7"^^xsd:integer .

# Feature/Location
<https://eurobis.org/id/location/76.98043-15.4356>
  a mr:Feature , dct:Location ;
  rdfs:label "Location at (76.98043 15.4356) - Hornsund, Spitsbergen_A 2/Greenland Sea"@en ;
  geo:hasCentroid <https://eurobis.org/id/point/76.98043-15.4356> ;
  mr:hasGeometry <https://eurobis.org/id/point/76.98043-15.4356> ;
  dcat:centroid "<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(76.98043 15.4356)"^^geo:wktLiteral ;
  dwc:geodeticDatum "EPSG:4326" ;
  dwciri:geodeticDatum <http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> ;
  dwc:minimumDepthInMeters "147"^^xsd:integer ;
  dwc:maximumDepthInMeters "147"^^xsd:integer ;
  dwc:decimalLatitude "76.98043"^^xsd:decimal ;
  dwc:decimalLongitude "15.4356"^^xsd:decimal ;
  dwc:locality "Hornsund, Spitsbergen_A 2/Greenland Sea" ;
  mr:isPartOf <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C16/current/05/> ;
  dwciri:inDescribedPlace <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C16/current/05/> .
```

Figure 33: BioEvent data using the marine observation ontology

In this example, specific properties regarding the depth in meters where the sample was taken are available and, thus, we can derive that the `BioEvent` is also a `Sampling` activity. The example also shows how to represent both the temporal and spatial dimensions. In particular, the spatial dimension can be articulated using Darwin Core' properties (`dwc:decimalLatitude` and `dwc:decimalLongitude`), but also relying on the `MarineRegions` ontology (representing a location as a `mr:Feature`) as well as the `GeoSPARQL` standard (for geographical coordinates). This richness of materialisation of RDF properties, enabled by the design and implementation choices we have done in the marine observation ontology, allows users to query this type of data through potentially the use of different standards of their interest.

Another relevant element of `EurOBIS` data is represented by records on occurrences of organisms. An example is provided in Figure 34 below.

occurrenceID	847166_urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:130097
eventID	hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812
basisOfRecord	Occurrence
occurrenceStatus	present
scientificNameID	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:130097
scientificName	Brada inhabilis
scientificNameAuthorship	(Rathke, 1843)

Figure 34: Example of an Occurrence record from EurOBIS

Figure 35 illustrates the RDF representation for the organism occurrence, linked to the previously described `BioEvent`.

```
# Occurrence
<https://eurobis.org/id/occurrence/243_847166_urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:130097>
  a marine-observation:OrganismOccurrence , dwc:Occurrence ;
  rdfs:label "Occurrence of Brada inhabilis (Rathke, 1843)"@en ;
  dct:identifier "847166_urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:130097" ;
  marine-observation:madeDuringEvent <https://eurobis.org/id/event/243_hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812> ;
  dwc:basisOfRecord "Occurrence" ;
  marine-observation:hasOccurrenceBasis <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/dwctype/Occurrence> ;
  marine-observation:hasOccurrenceStatus <https://eurobis.org/ns/occurrence-status/present> ;
  dwciri:occurrenceStatus <https://eurobis.org/ns/occurrence-status/present> ;
  marine-observation:isOfOrganismNamedAs <https://aphia.org/id/taxname/130097> .
```

Figure 35: Organism occurrence in LOD using the marine observation ontology

The example presented in Figure 35 illustrates an occurrence of an organism whose taxon name is identified in the Aphia's LOD for WoRMS with the Aphia ID 130097. This creates the link between species occurrences represented as LOD and species names represented as LOD.

Figure 36 then provides an example of `MeasurementOrFact`, in particular on the extent of the area of the seabed or shore observed or sampled.

eventID	hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812
measurementType	area
measurementTypeID	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/AREABEDS/
measurementValue	0.1
measurementUnit	squared metres
measurementUnitID	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UMSQ/
measurementRemarks	0.1 m ²

Figure 36: Example of a MeasurementOrFact record in EurOBIS

The corresponding RDF representation is provided below in Figure 37.

```
# Assertion~
<https://eurobis.org/id/assertion/243_hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812_AREABEDS>
  a marine-observation:Assertion , dwc:MeasurementOrFact ;
  rdfs:label "Assertion - area: 0.1 squared metres"@en ;
  marine-observation:madeDuringEvent <https://eurobis.org/id/event/243_hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812> ;
  marine-observation:hasObservableProperty <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/AREABEDS/> ;
  dwciri:measurementType <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/AREABEDS/> ;
  dwc:measurementType "area" ;
  marine-observation:hasObservationValue <https://eurobis.org/id/value/0.1-m2> ;
  dwciri:measurementValue <https://eurobis.org/id/value/0.1-m2> ;
  dwc:measurementValue "0.1"^^xsd:decimal ;
  dwciri:measurementUnit <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UMSQ/> ;
  dwc:measurementUnit "squared metres" ;
  dwc:measurementRemarks "0.1 m2" .

# Value~
<https://eurobis.org/id/value/0.1-m2>
  a top-level:Value ;
  rdfs:label "Value 0.1 Square metres"@en ;
  top-level:value "0.1"^^xsd:decimal ;
  top-level:hasUnitOfMeasure <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UMSQ/> .
```

Figure 37: Assertion in LOD using the marine observation ontology

The MeasurementOrFact is represented as an Assertion and linked to the event that represents the context for the assertion. The observable property, the value and the unit of measure are represented with the dedicated properties, also establishing links to concepts in the well-known controlled vocabularies managed by the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC).

Another example of MeasurementOrFact is shown in Figure 38. In this case, the record represents a statement on the number of individuals observed in the context of the organism occurrence described before.

eventID	hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812
occurrenceID	847166_urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:130097
measurementType	individualCount
measurementTypeID	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/OCOUNT01/
measurementValue	1

Figure 38: Example of a MeasurementOrFact record in EuroBIS

The corresponding RDF representation is provided below in Figure 39. The Assertion is linked to both the BioEvent and the OrganismOccurrence, and documents the number of observed individuals.

```
# Assertion-
<https://eurobis.org/id/assertion/243_847166_urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:130097_OC0UNT01>
  a marine-observation:Assertion , dwc:MeasurementOrFact ;
  rdfs:label "Assertion - individualCount: 1"@en ;
  marine-observation:madeDuringEvent <https://eurobis.org/id/event/243_hs2_2002-07_76.98043_147_381812> ;
  marine-observation:inTheContextOf <https://eurobis.org/id/occurrence/243_847166_urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:130097> ;
  marine-observation:hasObservableProperty <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/OCOUNT01/> ;
  dwciri:measurementType <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/OCOUNT01/> ;
  dwc:measurementType "individualCount" ;
  marine-observation:hasObservationValue <https://eurobis.org/id/value/1> ;
  dwciri:measurementValue <https://eurobis.org/id/value/1> ;
  dwc:measurementValue "1"^^xsd:integer .

# Value-
<https://eurobis.org/id/value/1>
  a top-level:Value ;
  rdfs:label "Value 1"@en ;
  top-level:value "1"^^xsd:integer .
```

Figure 39: Assertion in LOD using the marine observation ontology

7 SHACL Shapes

To provide a robust mechanism for data validation and quality control, we decided to rely on the SHACL standard to produce so-called *shapes*. SHACL⁴⁴ (Shapes Constraint Language) is a W3C standard for validating RDF graphs against a set of conditions, known as “shapes”. It operates as a constraint validation mechanism that can be applied to RDF data to ensure it conforms to specified requirements.

At its core, SHACL defines two main types of shapes: node shapes and property shapes. Node shapes describe constraints on nodes in the RDF graph (typically resources), while property shapes define constraints on the properties (predicates) of those nodes. These shapes can specify various types of constraints including cardinality restrictions (minimum/maximum number of values), datatype requirements, value ranges, and complex logical conditions.

SHACL shapes are themselves expressed in RDF, making them inherently interoperable with the data they validate. Similarly, the validation process produces a validation report in RDF format, detailing any constraint violations found in the target graph.

In the context of Linked Data Event Streams⁴⁵ (LDES), SHACL plays a crucial role in ensuring data quality and consistency as events flow through the system. As SHACL defines constraints on RDF data, in the context of LDES these constraints are used to define the expected structure of the data within the event stream. Therefore, by incorporating SHACL shapes, LDES provides a powerful tool for ensuring data quality and consistency, making it a reliable and trustworthy source of data for various applications. By defining a SHACL shape for the LDES, data producers can ensure that the members they add to the LDES adhere to the required structure, while data consumers can use the shape to validate and reason about the data they receive. The combination of SHACL’s validation capabilities with LDES’s streaming architecture creates a robust framework for maintaining high-quality, semantically consistent event streams.

The marine biodiversity domain presents peculiar data quality challenges, particularly when considering information from authoritative sources such as MarineRegions, WoRMS and EurOBIS. Each of these data sources maintains specific data structures, vocabularies, and quality requirements that reflect the complex nature of marine taxonomic and bio-geographic information.

These domain-specific requirements go beyond what can be expressed through ontological axioms alone. While ontologies provide the semantic foundation and conceptual relationships, they cannot capture, by design, operational constraints. SHACL shapes bridge this gap by complementing the ontological axiomatization with concrete, actionable data validation rules that can be automatically checked and enforced.

The SHACL shapes developed for these marine data sources encode both structural constraints (ensuring required properties are present with appropriate cardinalities) and

⁴⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

⁴⁵ We remind that LDES is the paradigm for publishing and consuming streams of linked data events adopted in the MAREGRAPH project for publishing as LOD the data from MarineRegions, WoRMS and EurOBIS

semantic constraints (validating that values conform to controlled vocabularies, reference valid external identifiers, and maintain logical consistency across related properties). This dual approach ensures that the resulting linked data not only conforms to the conceptual model defined by the ontology but also meets the practical quality standards.

In the following, we provide illustrative examples of SHACL shapes to clarify their role in validating marine biodiversity data and demonstrate how abstract validation requirements translate into concrete constraint definitions. These examples are selected to showcase different types of validation patterns and their practical applications within the marine data publication approach.

However, listing all SHACL shapes would be beyond the scope of this document, as the complete validation framework encompasses multiple individual constraints covering the full breadth of data structures and quality requirements. For comprehensive coverage and reference documentation of all shapes, including their complete definitions, we refer the reader to the already mentioned GitHub repository hosting the semantic assets⁴⁶, where the shapes are actively maintained and updated to reflect evolving data and community requirements.

7.1 MarineRegions

The production and publication of MarineRegions data as LOD and LDES actually preceded the MAREGRAPH project. However, to provide a complete picture of the overall landscape, we include an example of SHACL shapes for MarineRegions here as well.

```
@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix mr: <http://www.marineregions.org/ns/ontology#> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix geo: <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#> .

# Constraints on MRGeoObject
[] a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass mr:MRGeoObject ;
  sh:nodeKind sh:IRI ;

  # Required property
  sh:property [
    sh:path skos:prefLabel ;
    sh:datatype rdf:langString ;
    sh:minCount 1
  ] ;
```

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/MareGraph-EU/assets>

```
# Optional geometric property
sh:property [
  sh:path dcat:centroid ;
  sh:datatype geo:wktLiteral ;
  sh:maxCount 1 ;
  sh:minCount 0
] .
```

The fragment of SHACL shapes above, in simple terms, validates that marine geographic features have proper names in specific languages and can optionally include their center point coordinates.

More in detail, this shape validates any resource that is classified as an `mr:MRGeoObject` (a marine geographic object). The object itself must be identified by a URI, not just a text value.

Every marine geographic object must have at least one (`sh:minCount 1`) preferred label (`skos:prefLabel`). This label must be a language-tagged string (`rdf:langString`), meaning it includes both the text and the language it's written in (like "Mediterranean Sea"@en for English or "Mar Mediterraneo"@it for Italian).

In addition, a marine geographic entity can optionally have a centroid point (`dcat:centroid`) that represents its geographic center. If provided, this must be formatted as WKT (Well-Known Text) - a standard way of describing geometric shapes and points (`geo:wktLiteral`). An object can have at most one centroid (`sh:maxCount 1`), but it's not required to have any (`sh:minCount 0`).

7.2 WoRMS

Data validation rules are critically important for a taxonomic database like WoRMS. While the ontology modules presented in Section 5 provide a reference knowledge representation framework, SHACL shapes add the constraints to enforce data quality and structural integrity.

```
@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix taxon-name: <https://aphia.org/ns/taxon-name/> .

# Constraints on Taxon
[] a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass taxon-name:Taxon ;

# Optional parent Taxon
sh:property [
  sh:path taxon-name:hasParent ;
  sh:class taxon-name:Taxon ;
  sh:maxCount 1
] .
```

```
# Constraints on TaxonName
[] a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass taxon-name:TaxonName ;

  # Required single aphiaID
  sh:property [
    sh:path taxon-name:aphiaID ;
    sh:datatype xsd:integer ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1 ;
  ] .
```

The two SHACL shapes above validate specific aspects related to taxonomy and nomenclature (see Taxon name ontology module, Section 5.2).

The first SHACL shape validates that any `taxon-name:Taxon` can optionally have a parent relationship, but if it does have a parent, there can be only one. The parent must also be another `taxon-name:Taxon`. This enforces the tree-like hierarchical structure of the taxonomic classification in WoRMS, where each taxon has at most one direct parent.

The second shape ensures that every `taxon-name:TaxonName` must have exactly one AphiaID - a unique integer identifier used by the WoRMS database system. The constraint prevents taxonomic names from existing without proper identification or having multiple identifiers.

```
@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix td: <https://aphia.org/ns/distribution/> .

# Constraints on Distribution
[] a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass td:Distribution ;

  # Optional Invasiveness
  sh:property [
    sh:path td:hasInvasiveness ;
    sh:nodeKind sh:IRI ;
    sh:and (
      [ sh:class td:Invasiveness ]
      [ sh:class skos:Concept ]
    ) ;
    sh:message "The property td:hasInvasiveness must have an object that
      is of types td:Invasiveness and skos:Concept"@en ;
    sh:severity sh:Violation
  ] .
```

The SHACL shape above validates a specific aspect of distribution data (Section 5.3). In particular, it validates that any `td:Distribution` entity can optionally include invasiveness information. If invasiveness is specified (with the `td:hasInvasiveness` property), it must satisfy two requirements simultaneously: it must be both an instance of the `td:Invasiveness` class and a `skos:Concept` (suggesting the usage of a SKOS controlled vocabulary for defining possible entities representing invasiveness). The entity must be referenced by URI rather than being a literal value.

The shape also includes a custom error message explaining the dual-type requirement and marks violations as serious errors. This ensures that invasiveness classifications follow both the domain-specific taxonomy and general vocabulary standards, maintaining consistency in how invasive species status is recorded and categorised.

7.3 EurOBIS

Data validation rules are critically important also for biodiversity databases like EurOBIS. AS for the case of WoRMS, while the ontology module presented in Section 5.6 provides a reference knowledge representation framework, SHACL shapes add the needed constraints to enforce data quality and structural requirements for occurrence and observation data, as well as for related assertions.

```

@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix marine-observation: <https://eurobis.org/ns/marine-observation/>.
@prefix dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .

# Constraints on Event
[] a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass marine-observation:BioEvent ;

  # Required single date as literal
  sh:property [
    sh:path dct:date ;
    sh:nodeKind sh:Literal ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1
  ] ;

  # Required single location
  sh:property [
    sh:path marine-observation:occursIn ;
    sh:nodeKind sh:IRI ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1
  ] .

```

This SHACL shape validates marine observation events by enforcing critical spatiotemporal requirements, ensuring that every `marine-observation:BioEvent` has both essential dimensions (*when* and *where*) for biodiversity data. In line with the requirements and constraints of the OBIS data model, the shape guarantees that marine biodiversity observations can be properly situated in both time and space.

In particular, each event must have exactly one date (`dct:date`) recorded as a literal value, establishing the temporal context of the marine observation. In addition, each event must be linked to exactly one location (`marine-observation:occursIn`) referenced by URI, establishing the spatial context of where the marine observation took place.

```
@prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix marine-observation: <https://eurobis.org/ns/marine-observation/>.

# Constraints on OrganismOccurrence
[] a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetClass marine-observation:OrganismOccurrence ;

  # Required occurrence status - only Present or Absent allowed
  sh:property [
    sh:path marine-observation:hasOccurrenceStatus ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1 ;
    sh:in ( marine-observation:Present marine-observation:Absent )
  ] ;

  # Required organism name reference
  sh:property [
    sh:path marine-observation:isOfOrganismNamedAs ;
    sh:nodeKind sh:IRI ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1
  ] .
```

The SHACL shape above validates organism occurrence entities, ensuring that every marine organism occurrence (`marine-observation:OrganismOccurrence`) has two essential pieces of information: the occurrence status and taxonomic identification of the observed organism.

In particular, each occurrence must have exactly one status value, and it can only be either `marine-observation:Present` (organism was found) or `marine-observation:Absent` (organism was confirmed not present). This basically creates a controlled vocabulary for recording whether species were detected during observations. In addition, each occurrence must reference exactly one organism name via URI, linking the occurrence to specific taxonomic information. This ensures proper species identification is recorded for each observation.

8 Concluding Remarks

This document provides a comprehensive description of the ontologies developed within the MAREGRAPH project. These ontologies are organized into a cohesive network, developed using a specific methodology. This methodology was seamlessly integrated into the broader organizational processes introduced in Work Package 2, which has been mentioned in this deliverable.

All developed ontologies are publicly available on GitHub, serving as the primary reference point for the production of Linked Open Data as Linked Data Event Streams in Work Packages 4 and 5, and for facilitating interaction with external communities. This GitHub repository tracks various versions of the ontologies, ensuring transparency and traceability of changes. Furthermore, it provides associated SHACL shapes, which are essential for verifying and validating data quality against defined constraints of the ontologies.

It is important to acknowledge that ontologies are dynamic entities, inherently subject to continuous evolution. This adaptability is crucial as new requirements inevitably emerge from a variety of sources, ranging from the integration of novel datasets to fresh demands from stakeholders. Consequently, while this document presents the final versions of the ontologies comprising the MAREGRAPH knowledge graph, it is possible that additional changes and refinements to these semantic assets may be applied in the future to ensure their continued relevance and utility.

Bibliography

- [1] Borgo S. et al *DOLCE: A Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering*, in *Applied Ontology* 3 (2006) 1–3, IOS Press, <https://philarchive.org/archive/BORDAD-3>
- [2] Presutti V., Daga E., Gangemi A., Blomqvist E. *eXtreme Design with Content Ontology Design Patterns*, In *Proceedings of WOP (2009)* <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-516/pap21.pdf>
- [3] Gangemi A., Presutti V. *Ontology Design Patterns*. In *Chapter of the International Handbooks on Information Systems book series (INFOSYS)*, 2009.
- [4] Trojahn C. *Is Your data 6-Star?* <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2721/paper573.pdf>, 2020.
- [5] Corcho, O., Poveda-Villalón, M., Gomez-Perez, A. *Ontology Engineering in the Era of Linked Data*. *Bulletin of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*; 41(4), (2015). DOI: [10.1002/bult.2015.1720410407](https://doi.org/10.1002/bult.2015.1720410407).
- [6] Presutti V, Lodi G, Nuzzolese AG, Gangemi A, Peroni S, Asprino L. *The Role of Ontology Design Patterns in Linked Data Projects*, In the *Proceedings of Conceptual Modeling - 35th International Conference, ER 2016, Gifu, Japan, November 14-17, 2016*.
- [7] Peroni S., *Graffoo Specifications* <https://essepuntato.it/graffoo/specification/>
- [8] Lembo D., Santarelli V., Savo D. F., De Giacomo G., *Graphol: A Graphical Language for Ontology Modeling Equivalent to OWL 2*, In *Future Internet 2022*, 14(3), 78; <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi14030078>
- [9] Arenas M., Consens M., Mallea A., *Revisiting Blank Nodes in RDF to Avoid the Semantic Mismatch with SPARQL*, <https://www.w3.org/2009/12/rdf-ws/papers/ws23>
- [10] Hardisty, A.; Roberts, D. *The Biodiversity Informatics Community (2013). A decadal view of biodiversity informatics: Challenges and priorities*. *BMC Ecol.* 2013, 13.
- [11] Patterson, D.J.; Cooper, J.; Kirk, P.M.; Pyle, R.L.; Remsen, D.P. *Names are key to the big new biology*. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 2010, 25, 686–691.
- [12] Gadelha LMR Jr, de Siracusa PC, Dalcin EC, et al. *A survey of biodiversity informatics: Concepts, practices, and challenges*. *WIREs Data Mining Knowl Discov.* 2021; 11:e1394. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1394>
- [13] Remsen D. *The use and limits of scientific names in biological informatics*. In: Michel E (Ed.) *Anchoring Biodiversity Information: From Sherborn to the 21st century and beyond*. *ZooKeys* 550: 207–223. 2016. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.550.9546>
- [14] Franz, N. et al. *Names are not good enough: Reasoning over taxonomic change in the Andropogon complex*. *Semantic Web*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 645-667, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-160220>
- [15] Kennedy, J.B., Kukla, R., Paterson, T. *Scientific Names Are Ambiguous as Identifiers for Biological Taxa: Their Context and Definition Are Required for Accurate Data Integration*. In: Ludäscher, B., Raschid, L. (eds) *Data Integration in the Life Sciences*. DILS 2005. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 3615. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. 2005. https://doi.org/10.1007/11530084_8
- [16] Wiczorek J, Bloom D, Guralnick R, Blum S, Döring M, et al. *Darwin Core: An Evolving Community-Developed Biodiversity Data Standard*. *PLOS ONE* 7(1): e29715. 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0029715>
- [17] Darwin Core Task Group. 2009. Darwin Core. Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) <http://www.tdwg.org/standards/450>

- [18] Senderov, V., Simov, K., Franz, N. *et al.* *OpenBiodiv-O: ontology of the OpenBiodiv knowledge management system*. *J Biomed Semant* 9, 5 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-017-0174-5>
- [19] Peroni S. *The semantic publishing and referencing ontologies*. In: *Semantic Web Technologies and Legal Scholarly Publishing*. 1st edn. Cham: Springer: 2014. p. 121–93
- [20] Michel F., Gargominy O., Tercerie S. & Faron-Zucker C. *A Model to Represent Nomenclatural and Taxonomic Information as Linked Data. Application to the French Taxonomic Register, TAXREF*. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Semantics for Biodiversity (S4BioDiv) co-located with ISWC 2017*. CEUR vol. 1933. 2017
- [21] Klazenga N. *The Catalogue of Life Data Package (CoLDP) and the Taxon Concept Standard (TCS): A Comparison*. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 7: e110965. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.110965>
- [22] Zárate M., Braun G., Fillottrani P., Delrieux C., Lewis M. *BiGe-Onto: An ontology-based system for managing biodiversity and biogeography data*. *Applied Ontology* 15(4). 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3233/AO-20022>
- [23] Gangemi A., Lillo R., Lodi G., Nuzzolese A. G., Presutti V. *A Pattern-based Ontology for Internet of Things*, in *WOP@ISWC 2017*
- [24] Lippolis A.S, Lodi G., Nuzzolese A.G. *The Water Health Open Knowledge Graph*, in *Scientific Data* 12(1). 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04537-4>
- [25] De Pooter D., Appeltans W., Bailly N., et al. *Toward a new data standard for combined marine biological and environmental datasets - expanding OBIS beyond species occurrences*. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 5. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.5.e10989>